

FUND MANAGEMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Studies

By

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CERTIFICATION OF AUTHORSHIP

I hereby corroborate that I have researched and submitted the final draft of dissertation entitled “Fund Management and its impact on the financial performance of commercial Banks”. The work of this dissertation has not been submitted previously for the purpose of conferral of any degrees nor has it been proposed and presented as part of requirements for any other academic purposes.

The assistance and cooperation that I have received during this research work has been acknowledged. In addition, I declare that all information sources and literature used are cited in the reference section of the dissertation.

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Mr. Sagar Thapa has defended the research proposal entitled “Fund Management and its impact on the financial performance of commercial Banks” successfully. The research committee has registered the dissertation for further progress. It is recommended to carry out the work as per suggestions and guidance of supervisor and submit the thesis for evaluation and viva voce examination.

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Abbreviations

%	:	Percentage
&	:	And
AD	:	Anno Domini
ADBL	:	Agriculture Development Bank Limited
ANOVA	:	Analysis of Variance
BS	:	Bikram Sambat
BVPS	:	Book value per share
DPS	:	Dividend per share
EPS	:	Earnings per share
Etc.	:	Et cetera
Fig.	:	Figure
Ltd.	:	Limited
MPS	:	Market Price of Stock
N	:	Total number of observations
NBL	:	Nepal Bank Limited
No.	:	Number of
P-E ratio	:	Price-to-earnings ratio
RBBL	:	Rastriya Banijya Bank Limited
ROA	:	Return on Assets
Reg.	:	Registration
SE	:	Shareholder's Equity
SPSS	:	Statistical Package for Social Science

Abstract

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the comparative financial performance of ADBL, NBL and RBBL. It tries to evaluate the liquidity position of three government commercial banks and identify the relationship of net profit with respect to investment, deposit, and loan and advance of three government commercial banks. The study is mainly concerned with historical research. The study is based on the wide range of variables and factors influencing financial decisions of the banks. Comparative data of selected banks are presented in such a way, so as to make the research actually informative to the readers. It is not possible to study all the data related with all the bank of Nepal. There are all together 27 commercial banks in Nepal. Out of these, RBBL, ADBL and NBL are selected as sample for the purpose of study.

The study is based on secondary data. All the data are collected from the respective commercial bank's annual reports especially from profit and loss accounts, balance sheet and other publications made by the banks, which are the secondary data. Different tools and techniques are used to interpret and explain the data. Scientific calculator and simple laptop has been used to compute data. As per topic requirements, emphasis is given on financial tools. In addition, statistical tools are also used where applicable. The main methods, used for the Comparative Analysis of sample banks are financial tools and statistical tools.

This study fulfills the prevailing research gap about the in depth analysis of the financial performance which is the major concern of the shareholders and stakeholders. The study reveals that the financial position of all three government banks are good. All three banks are strong on the basis of financial performance measuring parameters.

Key words: Financial Performance, Deposit, Loan and Advances, Investment, Profit, Return on Assets (ROA), Dividend per Share (DPS), Earnings per Share (EPS) Non performing loan (NPL) Market Price of stock (MPS) Return on Equity(ROE)

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Finance can be defined as the art and science of managing money. Virtually all individuals and organizations earn or raise money and spend or invest it. Finance is concerned with the process, institutions, markets and instruments involved in the transfer of money among and between individuals, businesses and governments. Finance, in other words, can be defined as the management of the flows of money through an organization, whether it can be a corporation, school, bank or government agency. Finance concerns itself with the actual flows of money as well as any claims against money (Hampton, 1994).

The source of finance is most essential element for the establishment and operation of financial institute. Profit oriented institutions usually obtain these sources through ownership capital, public capital through issue of shares and debentures, borrowing through banking institution as credit or loan. Now a days, the essential sources of the organization for financial supporting is the credit, overdrafts and others provided by banking institution.

Although government banks have managed credit than other local commercial banks within short span of time, they have been facing a neck –to-neck competition against one another. Among this commercial banks, this research is based on mainly government banks, namely Rastriya Banijya Bank, Nepal Bank Limited and Agriculture Development Bank Limited. Commercial banks play a tremendous role in a developed or developing nation also helps to improve the economic sector of the country. Typically, commercial banks main motive is to make profit by providing quality services to the customers. In Nepal, there exist 27 commercial banks realizing their services at present. The study focus on evaluating the deposits utilization of the bank in terms of loans and advances and investments. They hold the deposit of money persons, government establishment and business. The study focuses on evaluating the deposits utilization of the bank in terms of loans and advances and investments and its contribution in the profitability of the bank. It also focuses on the contribution in the profitability of the bank. Commercial banks are the heart of financial system. They hold the deposit of many persons, government establishment and business units. They make fund available through their lending and investing activities to borrowing individual's business firms and government establishment. In doing so, they assist both the flow of

goods and services from the producers to consumers and the financial activities of the government. They provide a large portion of medium of exchange and they are the media through which monetary policy is affected. These facts show that commercial banking system of nation is important to the functioning of the economy.

Financial institution is currently viewed as catalyst in the process of economic growth of country. A key factor in the development of an economy is the mobilization of the domestic resources and intermediaries, the financial institution helps the process of resources mobilization. The importance of financial institutions in the economy has of late grown to an enormous extent. The government in turn is required to regulate their activities. So, the financial policies are implemented as per the requirement of the country (Thapa, 2014)

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. This term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time. It also can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation. There are many different ways to measure financial performance but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Line items such as revenue from operations, operating income or cash flow from operations can be used as well as total sales units. Furthermore, the analyst or investor may wish to look deeper into financial statements and seek out margin growth rates or any declining debt (Bhunia, Mukhuti and Roy, 2011).

Nowadays, when any new financial company floats share through capital market, very big congregation gathers to apply for owner certificate. It indicates their expectation on higher return of investment in shares. Most of the investor have little knowledge about the investment opportunities of such companies and having traditional concept that they can earn dividend from such shares and they forget the increasing no. of financial institutions and less possibility of investment opportunities. To mobilize their funds in a good manner, it should be invested in those potential sectors, which are appropriate from security, marketability, profitability and liquidity point of view.

Financial development is one of the key indicators of economic development of any country. Financial institution provides regular energy for investment, which is needed for economic development. In the financial sector, new institutions, instruments and financial innovations emerge in response to the need of national economy.

Commercial banks are a part of organized money market commercial banks mobilize savings in urban and rural areas and make them available to large and small industrial and trading units mainly for working capital requirements. Commercial banks acquire funds from the group of surplus, spending units and make these funds available to others deficit units. They have liabilities as well as assets. Their liabilities include deposits of different types, borrowings, bills payable, and other contra items types. Banks also have certain assets. These include cash, money at call or short notice, investments and bank credit of different types. Bank is one of the financial institutions, which regularly involves in finance. Simply, banks collect saving from individuals, and invest in different sectors. Nepal has a central bank, which coordinates industrial banks, commercial banks and other financial institutions, which are directly and indirectly involved in investment.

The performance of any commercial bank depends on the management of the bank's assets, liabilities, and capital. Increased competition has made efficient management essential for its survival. The bank managers should manage the assets and liabilities in such a way that it earns highest possible profit. In this regard, the bank manager has four primary concerns: liquidity management, assets management, liability management, and capital adequacy management.

To operate all commercial banks uniformly under single act "Commercial Bank Act 2031" was enacted. After the reestablishment of democracy, the government has taken liberal policy in banking sector that's why different private banks are getting permission to establish with the joint venture of other countries. Nabil is the first joint venture bank as Nepal Arab Bank. Similarly, two foreign commercial banks Nepal Indosuez Bank Ltd. and Grindlays Bank Ltd. entered in Nepal in the form of joint venture and the trend is continuing till today as many Nepalese owned banks are running. Today there are altogether 27 commercial banks in Nepal.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The performance of any commercial bank depends on the management of the bank's assets, liabilities, and capital. Increased competition has made efficient management essential for its survival. The bank managers should manage the assets and liabilities in such a way that it earns highest possible profit. In this regard, the bank manager has

four primary concerns: liquidity management, assets management, liability management, and capital adequacy management.

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. There are many different ways to measure financial performance but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Furthermore, the analyst or investor may wish to look deeper into financial statements and seek out margin growth rates or any declining debt. Gross profit margin, operating margin, net profit margin, return on capital employed, liquidity ratios, efficiency ratios and financial leverage are the measures of financial performance.

Ratio is the numerical relationship between two figures. It is expressed when one figure is divided by another. It is a powerful tool used as an index or yardstick for evaluating the financial performance. Financial analysis satisfies the interest of common stockholders, equality investors, creditors and management of the banks.

This research will highlight the financial problems of three government commercial banks, NBL, ADBL and RBBL. All three banks have achieved success in terms of profitability and market share. But we can't say that they will always be able to maintain profitability and market share. So, the management of the bank should always evaluate the financial performance of the bank.

Although the government banks (i.e. RBB, NBL and ADBL) are able to earn profit, there are some questions of problems which are as follows.

- i. What is the position of fund mobilization of government banks?
- ii. Are they efficient for mobilization of fund for better financial performance?
- iii. Are government banks maintaining sufficient liquidity positions?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Traditional financial ratio analysis has focused on the numbers. The value of this approach is that quantitative relations can be used to diagnose strength and weaknesses in the firm's performance. It provides a framework for financial planning and control. Financial managers need the information provided by analysis both evaluate the firm's past performance and to map future plans. Financial analysis concentrates on financial statement analysis, which highlights the key aspects of firm's operation. After identifying so much scopes and importance of financial analysis, I have decided to do research work on it by comparing the financial performance of government bank (ADBL, NBL and RBBL).

Each study or research is done for some objectives. So, this study also has some specific objectives. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the comparative financial performance of ADBL, NBL and RBBL. Other specific objectives are as follows: -

- a. To analyze the position of fund mobilization of government banks.
- b. To analyze the mobilization of fund for better financial performance by three government commercial banks.
- c. To evaluate the liquidity position of three government commercial banks.

1.4 Rationale of the study

Analysis of financial performance of any company is very important. Actually, on the basis of the financial analysis we can say that the concerned company is strong or not. The financial statements published by the banks gives the meaningful picture to the general public regarding the financial position of the banks. Thus, the analysis of these statements is necessary in order to give the full and clear-cut position and performance of the banks. This study mainly compares the financial performance of government bank (ADBL, NBL and RBBL) and compare the position of selected bank under the study, which encourage to improve the different position and performance of the selected banks. From data presentation and analysis, researchers find different strengths and weaknesses of the selective banks which is recommended to the banks for their further improvement

From the study, management can know about their weak points which can be corrected. The study helps the shareholders by making aware about the financial performance of their banks i.e. how properly their funds are utilized. Investors, depositors, debtors, stock brokers, competitors, market maker also will be benefited in their own way from this study. The official of the government, concerned ministry, Central Bank, Security Exchange who formulates and determines rules and policies regarding commercial banking operations make their work easier.

Banking Institutions definitely contribute and play an important role for domestic resource mobilization, economic development and maintain economic confidence of various segments and extend credit to people.

- This study has multidimensional significance in particular area of concerned banks which have been undertaken that justifies for finding out important points and facts to researchers, shareholders, brokers, traders, financial institution, and public knowledge.

- This study helps to find out the financial performance of concerned selected commercial banks and Government of Nepal to make plans and policies.
- This study provides input to policymakers of concerned selected banks for making plans and policies of the effective banking system.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

The study will have some limitations; basically the study is done for the partial fulfillment of Masters of Business Studies. Time constraints, financial problem and lack of research experience will be the primary limitation and other limitations are as follows

- The study will be concerned with only of 10 years' period (i.e. 2012 to 2021).
- The study will be related only with three government banks. The study deals only with three government banks namely RBBL, ADBL and NBL. The finding drawn may or may not be applicable to other various commercial of Nepal.
- Time and financial constraint are also major limitation of the study. The report has to be submitted within certain time period so this hinders the study to cover a large area.
- The researcher being a beginner in this area, this report cannot remain without flaws. But effort will be made to make the report with minimum error.
- The whole study will be based on secondary data collected from respective bank and internet. The result of this study resides on the accuracy of the sources.
- The result of this study resides on the accuracy of the sources.
- The study will focus only on financial aspects of the banks.

1.7 Organization of the report

The study will be divided into five chapters. They are introduction, review of literature, Research methodology, presentation and analysis of data and summary, conclusion and recommendation.

Chapter – I Introduction

This is the first chapter and is concerned with background of the study, development of the banking, commercial banks in Nepal, statement of problems, significance of the study, objectives of the study, limitation of the study and plan of the study.

Chapter – II Review of Literature

This part deals with different relevant articles, books, paper, thesis, etc.

Chapter – III Research Methodology

This chapter deals with research process, research design, sources of data, data collection process and research method. In method analysis, there are two parts (i.e. financial analysis and statistical analysis). In financial analysis, different ratios are mentioned whereas different statistical tools like trend analysis, correlation and regression analysis are mentioned under statistical analysis.

Chapter – IV Result and Discussion

In this chapter different ratios like liquidity ratio, profitability ratio, asset management ratio etc. are analyzed. Also, trend analysis, regression and correlation analysis is done.

Chapter – V Summary and Conclusion

This is the last chapter. In this chapter, summary of whole chapters and different results found in data analysis is mentioned. Various suggestions and recommendation for improving future performance is also given.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review is an essential part of all studies. It is a way to discover what other researchers have covered and left in the area. A critical review of the other literature helps the researchers to develop a thorough understanding and insight into previous research works that relates to the present study. It is a way to avoid investigation problems that have already been definitely answered. Thus a literature review, the process of locating, obtaining, reading and evaluating the research literature is the area of the student's interest (Wolff and Pant, 2005).

The purpose of literature review is to find out what research studies have been conducted in one's chosen field of study and what remains to be done. The primary purpose of literature review is to learn not to accumulate.

In this chapter the overall concept and view of 'financial Performance' will be streamlined by making comprehensive review of relevant literature related to this study which would enable us to know the comparative strength and weakness of the chosen banks and the opportunities/threats they possess in the dynamic environment. The review of literature is arranged in the following order:

- Conceptual Framework
- Review of Journals and Articles
- Review of Thesis
- Research Gap

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Financial analysis is the process of determining the significant operating and financial characteristics of a firm from accounting data and financial statements. The goal of such analysis is to determine the efficiency and performance of the firm's management, as reflected in the financial records and reports.

The analysis is attempting to measure the firm's liquidity, profitability and other indications that describe whether the business is conducted in a rational and orderly way or not. If a firm doesn't achieve financial norms for its industry or relationships among data are not seen reasonable, the analysts' notes down the deviations.

The burden of explaining the apparent problems may then be placed upon management (Hampton, 2006:98). Financial analysis is the process of identifying the financial strengths and weakness of the firm by properly establishing relationship between the

items of the balance sheet and the profit and loss account (Pandey, 1999:108). Financial statement analysis involves a comparison of a firm's performance with that other firm in the same line of business. Financial analysis is used to determine the firm's financial position in order to identify its current strength and weakness and suggests actions that might enable the firm to take advantages of its strengths and correct its weakness. Financial analysis of a firm's helps to find the answer of following questions:

- Is the profit of business firms adequate or enough?
- Do investors want to buy shares of company or not?
- Do business firm utilize its limited resources in effective way?
- What is the capital structure of the firms?
- Do the business firms effectively manage its current assets to pay liabilities?

2.1.1 Finance and Financial Performance

Finance can be defined as the art and science of managing money. It can also be defined as procurement of funds and its effective utilization in the business. Finance is a broad term that describes two related activities: the study of how the money is managed and the actual process of acquiring needed funds. Because individuals, business and government entities all need funding to operate, the field is often separated into three sub categories: personal finance, corporate finance and public finance. Virtually all individuals and organizations earn or raise money and spend or invest it. Finance is concerned with the process, institutions, markets and instruments involved in the transfer of money among and between individuals, businesses and governments. Finance, in other words, can be defined as the management of the flows of money through an organization, whether it can be a corporation, school, bank or government agency. Finance concerns itself with the actual flows of money as well as any claims against money (Hampton, 1994).

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. There are many different ways to measure financial performance but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Furthermore, the analyst or investor may wish to look deeper into financial statements and seek out margin growth rates or any declining debt. Gross profit margin, operating margin, net profit margin, return on capital employed, liquidity ratios, efficiency ratios and financial leverage are the measures of financial performance. Ratio analysis is defined as relationship between two accounting figure expressed mathematically.

Ratio is the numerical or an arithmetical relationship between two figures. It is expressed when one figure is divided by another. Ratio refers to the relationship expressed in a mathematical term between two individual figures or group of figures connected with each other in some logical manner and are selected from financial statement of concern.

It is found by dividing one number by the other. Ratio analysis is a powerful tool of financial analysis. A ratio is defined as "the indicated quotient of two mathematical expressions and as the relationship between two or more things". In financial analysis a ratio is used as a benchmark for evaluating the financial position and performance of a firm (Pandey, 1999:109).

Ratio analysis is the process of determining and interpreting numerical relationship based on financial statements. A ratio is a statistical yardstick that provides a measure of the relationship between to variable and figures. This relationship can be express as percent (cost of goods sold as a percentage of sales) or as a quotient (current assets as a certain number of times the current liabilities) (Kuchhal, 1976:21). Ratio is used as an index or yardstick for evaluating the financial position and performance. It helps analysis to make quantitative judgment about the financial position and performance of business firm. It helps to measure the profitability, solvency and performance of any business firm.

Ratio can be classified in a number of ways keeping in view the particular purpose. The ratio can be classified into following four categories:

- Liquidity ratio.
- Leverage ratio or capital structure ratio or solvency ratio.
- Activity ratio or turnover ratio or assets management ratio.
- Profitability ratio

Each of these types has a special use for the financial analyst. These ratios are also helpful for managerial control and for providing a better understanding of what outside suppliers of capital expect in the way of financial condition and performance. The usefulness of the ratio depends upon the knowledge and experience of the financial analyst who employs them. By themselves, financial ratios are fairly meaningless; they must be analyzed on a comparative basis.

A comparison of ratio of firms over same industry is important in evaluating changes and trends in the firm's financial condition and profitability. This comparison may be

historical; it may also include an analysis of the future based upon projected financial statements. Ratios may also be judged in comparison with those of similar firms in the same line of business and when appropriate, with an industry average.

The commercial bank has its own role and contribution in the economic development. Principally commercial banks accept deposits and advance loan and mobilize savings in urban and rural areas and make them available to large and small industrial and trading units mainly for working capital requirements. It is a resource for the economic development, it maintains economic confluence of various segments and extends credit to people (Ronald, 1991:87).

Commercial bank is a corporation, which accepts demand deposits and makes short-term loans to business enterprises, regardless of the scope of its other service (American Institution of Banking, 1972:345). The objective of financial analysis is to capsule how efficiently a company employs its assets and how it has chosen to finance the acquisition and carrying cost of those assets. This is accomplished by analyzing the relationships between an enterprise's operating result (income statement) and its financial structure (balance

Ratio analysis a widely used tool of financial analysis, it is defined as systematic use of ratio to interpret the financial statement so that the strengths and weakness of a firm as well as its historical performance and current condition can be determined (Khan and Jain, 1996:60). Ratios are relationship expressed in mathematical terms between figures which have a cause and effect relationship or which are connected with each other in some other manner.

Ratio analysis satisfies the interests of investor creditors, government, institutions and other to form their opinions for enabling them to have guideline towards effective decision making (Shrestha, 1980:255). Ratio analysis is one of the most commonly used techniques in the analysis of financial statement and evaluation of managerial performance. The analysis points out the problems. There are many parties who often refer to financial ratio in order to keep track of their investment performance or for some other reasons of their interest (Pradhan, 1992:35).

2.2 Review of Journals and Articles

The opinions or views expressed regarding commercial banks and their activities on journals, book and booklets, magazines, etc. are focused as follows:

Jha, Sujita (2021) analyzed the financial performance of commercial banks in Nepal in her article, “A comparison of financial performance of commercial banks: A case study of Nepal”. The objective of this study was to compare the financial performance of different ownership structured commercial banks in Nepal based on their financial characteristics and identify the determinants of performance exposed by the financial ratios, which were based on CAMEL Model. Eighteen commercial banks for the period 2015 to 2020 were financially analyzed. In addition, econometric model (multivariate regression analysis) by formulating two regression models was used to estimate the impact of capital adequacy ratio, non-performing loan ratio, interest expenses to total loan, net interest margin ratio and credit to deposit ratio on the financial profitability namely return on assets and return on equity of these banks. The results show that public sector banks are significantly less efficient than their counterpart are; however domestic private banks are equally efficient to foreign-owned (joint venture) banks. Furthermore, the estimation results reveal that return on assets was significantly influenced by capital adequacy ratio, interest expenses to total loan and net interest margin, while capital adequacy ratio had considerable effect on return on equity.

Ongore, Vincent Okoth (2021) in their article “Determinants of Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya“ studies on moderating effect of ownership structure on bank performance are scanty. To fill this glaring gap in this vital area of study, the authors used linear multiple regression model and Generalized Least Square on panel data to estimate the parameters. The findings showed that bank specific factors significantly affect the performance of commercial banks in Kenya, except for liquidity variable. But the overall effect of macroeconomic variables was inconclusive at 5% significance level. The moderating role of ownership identity on the financial performance of commercial banks was insignificant. Thus, it can be concluded that the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya is driven mainly by board and management decisions, while macroeconomic factors have insignificant contribution.

Shrestha Purna Man (2021) studies the financial performance of commercial banks in his studies “Determinants of Financial Performance of Nepalese Commercial Banks: Evidence from Panel Data Approach”. The impact of bank specific factors on the financial performance of Nepalese commercial banks is analyzed in this paper. The financial performance is measured by using return on assets (ROA). Similarly, managerial efficiency (ME), liquidity (LIQ), credit risk (CR), assets quality (AQ) and

operational efficiency (OE) is used as proxy of bank specific factors. This study used panel data of 17 commercial banks for the period of 2010/11 to 2017/18. Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test showed that Pooled Regression model is not appropriate and Hausman test concluded that Fixed Effect model is appropriate rather than Random Effect model. Using the Fixed Effect model; this study concludes that bank specific factors have significant impact on financial performance of Nepalese commercial banks. Finally, this study reveals that ME, AQ and OE have significant positive impact, and CR has negative impact on the financial performance of Nepalese commercial banks.

Bhandari, Rajan (2021), in "Policy won't support achievement of economic growth target" explained that monetary policy (2021-22) has tightened the credit expansion to keep inflation at the desired level. In his view monetary policy will not support the government's target of achieving economic growth rate of 7 % because private sector development is fundamental for accelerated growth. He expected the central bank to address the current scenario of credit crunch by reducing the statutory liquidity ratio as banks have to flush liquidity at the moment. The monetary policy has taken an objective to minimize the volatility of interest rates, expand credit to productive sector, expand financial outreach at remote places, which are commendable. It has also corrected the direct lending provision to the deprived sector by commercial banks.

Murarka, Pashupati (2021), in "NRB didn't ensure sustainability on interest rate on loan" explained that the monetary policy 2020-21 has failed to ensure sustainability on interest rates on loans the high rate of interest rate on loans being taken by banks and financial institutions and the instability in the interest rate are the chief problems that industries are facing today. Though we have repeatedly urged the government and Nepal Rastra Bank to insure investor that they get loans at low interest rate, the NRB didn't address this problem of the private sector in the new monetary policy. Similarly, the expansion of NRB's refinancing fund to Rs. 200 million from existing Rs.100 million is not enough. Likewise, the monetary policy 2020-21 will certainly hit the real estate sector lending in Kathmandu valley has been reduced to 50 percent of the value of the property from the existing 60 percent.

Poudel, Danda Pani (2020), in "Central Banking practices and evolving challenges to Nepal Rastra Bank" explained that NRB as a central bank is an apex authority to guide the overall financial system of the country whereas it has multiple role to play in the

economy. The NRB in its earlier days focused particularly in the areas of issuance and circulation of the Nepalese currency, maintaining exchange rate stability, capital mobilization and development of banking and financial institutions. As such, the NRB is the regulator and supervisor of the institutions like commercial banks, development banks, finance companies, microfinance development banks, financial cooperatives, NGOs, which are licensed by NRB to operate. As such, the NRB's functions have been concentrated from the typical traditional central banking to institutional development, development finance, resource mobilization and their productive allocation, regulation, supervision, formulation and implementation of monetary and foreign exchange policies. Obviously, the NRB as a central bank has to be careful in maintaining the price level and inflation which comes under the responsibility of monetary policy. Similarly, looking at the mushrooming growth of the financial sector due mainly to an easy task of making business, maintaining financial stability is a challenging job for central bank including the external sector stability.

Pant, Bhubanesh (2019), in "Nepalese Financial System: Policy Development and Challenges" stated that financial markets in many ways are the backbone of an economy. A well regulated financial sectors leads to an efficient transformation of saving to investment, ensuring that resources are deployed where they earn the highest returns. A strong financial system and the orderly evolution of financial markets are the major prerequisites for financial stability and economic progress. A healthy financial system is the one that effectively fosters resource mobilization for capital accumulation and determines efficient allocation of resources. It is important to remember that success of any financial system, in its resource mobilization and allocation functions, depends on its ability to offer the public a variety of assets (money as a medium of exchange, earning assets, pension funds etc.) corresponding to the various needs and preferences of economic agents. A clear understanding and recognition of this fact is very important to formulate appropriate policies to enable the financial system to function properly and efficiently. The test of the strength of a country's financial sectors is its capability to make available the appropriate types of institutions and financial instruments that can support economic growth. The NRB's challenge is to build up a financial system that is supportive of growth, and dynamic enough to change and fulfill the evolving demands of a real economy.

Sharma, Hari Bhakta (2017), in "suggestions of the private sector have been overlooked" stated that the government has overlooked all the major suggestion that the confederation of Nepalese Industries (CNI) had given for incorporation in the monetary policy for 2017-18. Though they asked Nepal Rastra Bank to reduce the cash reserve ratio (CRR) for banks and financial institutions by one percent point as doing so would address the credit crunch and increase BFI's loanable funds, their suggestion has been ignored in the monetary policy. Similarly, the monetary policy 2017-18 has not given emphasis on promoting investment and economic growth in the country. Though NRB has increased its refinancing funds to Rs.200 million from existing Rs 100 million, this can hardly facilitate big projects in the country. CNI believes that such refinancing funds should be of at least RS 100 billion.

Shrestha, Manohar Krishna (2015), in "Money Creation and Destruction by Banks" stated that the banks have power to create money in the form of credit cards, checkable deposits and others accounts that can be used for payments of purchase of goods and services. Banks generate profits by accepting cash through demand deposits and advance loans or credit to customers. Increase in deposits means increase in the supply of money in the country. The banking industry is able to increase the deposits by granting loans and advances to customers. By accepting deposits and granting loans and advances, banking system creates and destroys millions of money in banking industry in the economy. This power of the bank to expand deposits through expansion of their loans and advances is known as credit or money creation which is concern with deposits expansion.

Gurung, Rajesh (2014), in "General Principles of Bank Management" stated that the performance of any commercial bank depends on the management of the bank's assets, liabilities and capital. Increased competition has made efficient management essential for its survival. The bank managers should manage its assets and liabilities in such a way that it earns highest possible profit. In this regard, the bank manager has four primary concerns: liquidity management, assets management, liability management and capital adequacy management.

The bank should always make sure that it has enough ready cash to pay its depositors. Whenever, the bank fails to maintain sufficient liquid assets that provide wrong information in the market. As a result, bank may undergo insolvent. The bank manager must pursue an acceptably low level of risk by acquiring assets that have a low rate of

default. The successful banks also diversify its assets holding into so many different assets to reduce the level of risks.

The liability management is concerned with the management of bank's funding. The key purposes are to lower funding costs, control interest rate risk and manage liquidity. Finally, the capital adequacy management is crucial to bank management that the manager must decide the amount of capital the bank should maintain and then acquire the needed capital.

2.3 Review of Thesis

Shrestha, Anita (2007), conducted her thesis on "*Financial Performance Analysis of commercial Banks with reference to Nepal Investment Bank Ltd. and NABIL.*" and set up the objectives to analyze the financial strength and weakness of concern banks using financial tools and statistical tools and also to provide suggestions for its improvements. She found that liquidity ratio, leverage ratio and financial indicators of NABIL were better position than NIBL and turnover ratio of NIBL was in better position than NABIL. The study suggested both banks to review their overall capital structure and investment portfolio to make better mix capital structure, not to limit their activities within the urban areas only and to introduce new banking systems and improve their service.

Adhikari, Ishwori Prasad (2007), conducted his master's thesis on "*Credit Management of Everest Bank Limited*" had the main objective of examining the impact of deposit in liquidity, evaluate various stages in loan management procedure, analyze the lending efficiency of banks. He reached to the conclusion that EBL had sufficient liquidity. Loan loss provision of EBL had been increasing day by day. Due to political disturbances in the country credit takers were not getting good return from their investment sectors. On that situation credit customers did not return money of the bank in the stipulated time period therefore the non performing loans of the bank had increased. Equity portion of the bank was slightly increasing in the recent years due to issue of directives by Nepal Rastra Bank to increase the paid-up capital of the bank.

Acharya, Santosh (2012) conducted his master's thesis on "Investment Practice of Commercial Banks with reference of Bank of Kathmandu and NABIL Bank" with the main objective of evaluating the investment policies, fund mobilization and utilization, risk and profitability position of the concern banks. He found that the liquidity position of BOK was comparatively better than that of NABIL. Cash and bank balance to total

deposit ratio of BOK was higher than NABIL. Loan and advances to current assets ratio of BOK was slightly lower than NABIL. That shows that both banks had utilized their funds to gain maximum profit. From the analysis of asset management ratio it was found that BOK has better managed its assets. The loan and advances to total deposit ratio of BOK was higher than NABIL. It shows BOK had mobilized its more deposit on loan and advances. The total investment to total deposit ratio of BOK was lower than NABIL. Investment on government securities to total working fund ratio of BOK was higher than NABIL. It showed BOK had utilized its more portion of total working fund on government securities. Investment on share and debentures to total working fund ratio of BOK was slightly better than NABIL. The analysis of profitability ratio showed that NABIL was in better position than BOK. Return on total assets of NABIL was higher than BOK. It showed that BOK fails to earn higher profit on its working fund. The analysis of risk ratio showed that the credit risk ratio of BOK was higher than NABIL. It showed BOK has provided higher portion on loan which involves high risk but it can also provide high return if it is secure loan. The capital risk of NABIL was higher than BOK. This showed that there is high risk for NABIL but there is chance to high profit too.

Thapa, Pradip (2013), conducted his master's thesis on "*Analysis of Financial Performance of Himalayan Bank Limited*" had main objective to examine the financial statement of the bank and analyze them to see the financial soundness, and finally reached to the conclusion that the bank had utilized their resource in proper order in profit generating sectors and the bank had employed qualified personal and make them equipped with all the technical knowledge of banking. Therefore, there is no doubt that banking has been operating smoothly and succeeds in becoming the pillars of economic system of the country. Banks has direct contribution to the shareholder, depositors and government.

Pokhrel, Saroj Kumar (2012), conducted his master thesis on "*Financial performance Analysis of Everest Bank Limited*" had a major objective to evaluate the liquidity, efficiency and profitability of EBL and to find out the relationship of total investment, loans and advances and net profit with total deposits. He reached to the conclusion that the bank had good financial position. EBL had been maintaining a steady growth rate over this period. EBL earned a net profit of Rs. 296.4 million for the fiscal year 2006/07 and this comes to be 24.96% more as compared to the same period in the previous fiscal

year. EBL earned an operating profit of Rs.597.9 million for the fiscal year 2006/07 and this comes to be 31.96% more as compared to the same period in the previous fiscal year. It had total deposits of Rs. 1818.6 million for the fiscal year 2006/07 and this comes to be 31.8% more than the deposits of previous year. Thus, overall performance of EBL had seems to be satisfactory.

Ojha, Raj Kumar (2014), conducted his thesis on "*A Comparative Study of Financial Performance of Nepal Investment Bank limited and Everest Bank Limited*" had a objective to examine and evaluate the performance of two joint venture bank and reached to the conclusion that total deposit, total investment, loan and advance and net worth have been growing in faster pace in NIBL. Current ratios of both the banks were similar and less than the standard ratio i.e. 2:1. Deposits of NIBL were comparatively higher than EBL. Ratio of cash and bank balance to total deposit is lower for NIBL than EBL. This proved that NIBL had utilized more amounts in loans and advances rather than for liquidity purpose. While calculating the leverage ratio, it was found that NIBL was using more debt than equity. It leads to increase in interest expenses. Debt is riskier than equity. Ratio of NPAT to Total Assets and NPAT to Total Deposit, both is higher for NIBL. So from the profitability point of view, NIBL was better than EBL. EBL had incurred more expenses for staffs. More staff expenses may lead to the increase in motivation level of staffs and also leads to the increase in expenses of the bank. Interest earned on total assets for both the banks were similar. It means NIBL had shown better profitability due to more other incomes rather than the interest income.

Maharjan, Shyam (2015), conducted his master's thesis on "*Investment analysis of commercial Banks in Nepal*" (A case study of Nepal Investment Bank Limited, Himalayan Bank Limited, Nepal SBI Bank Limited, Everest Bank Ltd. and Bank of Kathmandu Ltd.) with the objectives of analyzing the present position regarding investment policy, investment trend and to identify investment sector of selected commercial banks. After the study and analysis of given data he concluded that all sample banks were running in profit. NIBL was the oldest bank of given other banks. It means NIBL collected more deposits and invested in different sectors. From the analysis of data, HBL was also running successfully and the growth ratio of investment is higher than other banks. It had collected more deposits and investment than that of others banks but its growth rate of deposits and loans and advances is less than that of others banks. EBL was also running successfully, and the growth ratio of deposits was

higher than other banks. Its growth rate of investment and loans and advances was also increasing.

Dahal, Manila (2016), conducted her master's thesis on "A Study on investment patterns of Bank of Kathmandu and Kumari bank limited" had objectives to study and examine the fund mobilization and investment practice of the concerned banks, to analyze the liquidity, assets managing, profitability, growth and risk of concerned banks and to evaluate the relationship between deposits and loans and advances, deposits and total investment and deposits and net profit and trend analysis of above variables. She found that BOKL has higher capability to meet current obligation though it has higher cash and bank balance to total deposits ratios and higher current ratio. The proportion of investment on government securities of BOKL was also considerably higher than KBL. Assets management of BOKL seems better than that of KBL. From profitability point of view, return on loans and advances reveals that BOKL had higher average return on loans and advances than Kumari Bank Limited.

Gautam, Ramji (2018), examines the determinants of financial performance of commercial banks in Nepal in his article, "Determinants of financial performance: An evidence from Nepalese commercial banks". In order to investigate the determinants of financial performance, 10 commercial banks have been taken as samples covering the period of time from 2006/07 to 2016/17. Data are collected from annual reports of the respective banks. Multiple linear regression models have been employed for the analysis of data. The result shows a positive relationship between return on assets with capital adequacy ratio, management efficiency, and gross domestic product whereas negative with assets quality and liquidity management. It is evident from the findings that the financial performance of commercial banks are strongly affected by capital adequacy ratio, management efficiency, gross domestic product, liquidity management and assets quality.

Gautam, Kedar Raj (2020), attempts to examine the financial performance and factors influencing financial performance of Nepalese financial depository institutions in the framework of CAMEL in his research, "Financial Performance Analysis of Nepalese Financial Institutions in the Framework of CAMEL". This study is based on descriptive cum casual research design. This study is based on secondary data which was extracted from various publications published by Nepal Rastra Bank such as banking and financial statistics, financial stability report and bank supervision report. All

commercial banks, development banks, and finance companies are taken as population of the study. The study deals with financial performance analysis of entire population covering five years from 2014/15 to 2018/19. The variables such as capital adequacy, assets quality, management efficiency, earnings and liquidity are used to analyze financial performance. Descriptive as well as pooled regression analysis was used to assess the relationship among the variables. Descriptive analysis shows that financial institutions in each category meet NRB standard regarding capital adequacy. On the basis of capital adequacy and earnings, finance companies stand at first, on the basis of assets quality, development banks stand at first and on the basis of management efficiency, commercial banks stand at first. Finance companies store high liquidity as compared to other class financial institutions. The regression analysis shows that return on assets, ROA has significant positive relationship with capital adequacy and ROE but ROA has significant negative relationship with assets quality. However, return on equity, ROE has significant positive relationship with assets quality and ROA but ROE has significant negative relationship with capital adequacy. Capital adequacy and assets quality play major role to maximize ROA and ROE of financial institutions.

Kandel, Santosh (2021), analyzes the financial performance of commercial banks in his studies, "Analysis of financial performance of commercial banks of Nepal using CAMEL approach". This paper aims to analyze the performance of the commercial banks using CAMEL framework and analyze their performance on average basis with selected samples. The financial sectors have always been the economic drive of Nepal holding large share market of the country. The good performance of the financial institutions must for the strong and growing economy. Therefore, this research paper makes analysis of the variables of the CAMEL framework to find the important factors influence the commercial bank's performance. The data analysis reveals that the main factor affecting both ROA and ROE are earning quality and rest capital adequacy, assets quality and liquidity have moderating influence on performance of banks. The management efficiency show minimal impact on the ROA and ROE as per the findings. The factors that were selected for this research paper may have minimal influence but other factors of the management may have direct influence on performance of the banks.

Rai et al. (2021), studied entitled "Determinants of financial performance in Nepalese financial institutions" taking return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and net

interest margin (NIM) as the dependent variables while capital adequacy ratio, assets quality, management efficiency, liquidity management, GDP growth rate and inflation were chosen as independent variables with the data of 2015 to 2020. They found the result that higher the capital adequacy ratio, management efficiency and liquidity management, higher would be the return on equity and return on assets. Likewise higher the GDP growth rate and inflation rate, higher would be the return on equity and return on assets. The study also indicates that higher the assets quality lower would be the return on equity and return on assets. The study also revealed that larger the capital adequacy ratio and assets quality, higher would be the net interest margin. It also shows that higher the management efficiency, liquidity management, GDP growth rate and inflation rate, higher would be the net interest margin.

Murerwa (2021), conducted a thesis research on the topic of "Determinants of banks' financial performance in developing economies: Evidence from Kenyan commercial banks, Nepal is also one of the developing country like Kenya, the findings of the African developing country can be relatable to Nepalese banking industry. Main objective of his thesis was to evaluate the macroeconomic factors which influence the financial performance of the commercial banks in Kenya. On the basis of his study, he concluded that industry specific factors are regarded as a critical pointer of the financial performance of the Kenyan commercial banks. External market structure indeed affects the financial performance of the Kenyan banks. Moreover, he argues that the impact posed macroeconomic factors on the financial performance is minimal.

2.4 Research Gap

Research Gap is the difference between previous works done and the present research works. Earlier researches conducted by many researchers in the similar topic "Comparative Financial Performances of commercial banks" are very useful and appreciated by the personals in the various related fields, including academicians, bankers, shareholders and the general public. Those dissertations in a great extent have been successful in analyzing the financial performance of concerned private bank and JVB. The policy of Nepal Rastra Bank is being changed time to time. So the updated study over the change of time frame is major concern for the researchers and concerned organizations as well. The study is based on the more recent financial data.

No research has been undertaken regarding the comparative analysis of the financial performance of three government banks. But some researchers have done the

comparative study of other joint venture banks. Financial analysis is the major function of every bank for evaluating the financial performance. Therefore, it is major concern of stakeholders to know the financial condition of the bank.

Government banks are the leading commercial banks of the country having huge market share and investment activities. These banks have significant impact for developing the economy of the country. Financial performance is being changed every year due to the various environment of the country. Hence, this study fulfills the prevailing research gap about the in depth analysis of the financial performance which is the major concern of the shareholders and stakeholders.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Research methodology is a systematic way to solve the research problem. In other words, research methodology describes the methods and process applied in the entire aspect of the study. Research methodology refers to the various sequential steps to be adopted by a researcher in studying a problem with certain objective. Thus the overall approach to the research is presented in this chapter. This chapter consists of research design, sample size and selection process, data collection procedure and data processing techniques and tools.

3.2 Research Design

A research design is the specification of methods and procedures for acquiring the information needed. It is the overall operational pattern of framework for the project that stipulates what information is to be collected, from which sources and by what procedures.

Thus a research design is a plan for the collection and analysis of data. For research there exists different types of research design like; Historical research, Descriptive research, Case study research, Field study research, Analytical research, True experimental research and so on. This is mainly concerned with historical research. If applicable, sometimes descriptive analytical approach may also be used. But general, to analyze the comparative analysis of the government banks, past historical data are used. The relevant and needed data have been collected from various publications of different commercial banks. The study is based on the wide range of variables and factors influencing financial decisions of the banks. Comparative data of selected banks are presented in such a way, so as to make the research actually informative to the readers.

3.3 Population and Sample

The term "population" or universe for research means the universe of research study in which the research is based (Wolf and Pant, 2000:75). Population is the entire group of people, events or things of interest that a researcher wishes to investigate. When some of the elements are selected with the intention of finding out something about the populations that group of elements are referred as a sample and the process of selection is called sampling. It is not possible to study all the data related with all the bank of Nepal. There are all together 27 commercial banks in Nepal. Out of these, RBBL, ADBL and NBL are selected as sample for the purpose of study.

3.4 Sources of Data

The researcher can use two methods of data collection i.e. Primary and Secondary data. Primary data are the data collected directly from the site. It can be called as first hand data. These data are very reliable if researcher can reach the correct destination with required tools. Secondary data are second hand data collected from different other sources such as magazines, newspapers, journals, second persons, etc. The study is based on secondary data. All the data are collected from the respective commercial bank's annual reports especially from profit and loss accounts, balance sheet and other publications made by the banks, which are the secondary data. Likewise, some other related information is gathered from related banks and related agencies like Nepal Rastra Bank, Nepal Stock Exchange Limited. Various data and information are also collected from the journals, periodical bulletins, magazines, newspapers and internet.

- Annual Reports of Rastriya Banijya Bank limited (RBBL).
- Annual Reports of Agriculture Development Bank Limited (ADBL).
- Annual Reports of Nepal Bank limited (NBL).
- Precious related research and dissertations.
- Books, Magazines, Newspapers and Journals.
- Internet and Other sources.

3.5 Data Processing Techniques

After the necessary data has been collected, relevant facts and figure have to be tabulated under the different headings. Such tables and formats are to be interpreted and explained as required. Different tools and techniques are used to interpret and explain the data. Scientific calculator and simple laptop has been used to compute data.

3.6 Data Analysis Tools

In order to get the concrete results from this research, data are analyzed using different types of tools. As per topic requirements, emphasis is given on financial tools. In addition, statistical tools are also used where applicable. The main methods, used for the Comparative Analysis of sample banks are financial tools and statistical tools.

3.6.1 Financial Tools

Financial tools help to identify the financial Strengths and Weaknesses of the firm. In spite of various financial tools available, the research has primarily stressed on Ratio Analysis assuming it to be the most suitable one. A ratio is a number expressed in terms of other number and it expresses quantitative relation between any two variables

Moreover, it is used as a technique to quantify the relationship between two sets of financial data taken from either profit and loss a/c or balance sheet. It provides information relating to comparative study of financial data in relation to others (Lawrence, 1988:275). Ratio can be calculated between any two items of financial statements. It means there may be as many ratios as there is the number of items. But under the ratio analysis technique, it is not practical to work out all the ratios. Hence only the required ratios have been worked out. The calculated ratios have been grouped into the following headings.

A) Ratio Analysis

Ratio is the numerical or an arithmetical relationship between two figures. It is expressed when one figure is divided by another. Ratio analysis is the process of determining and interpreting numerical relationship between figures of financial statements. Ratio is used as an index for evaluating the financial position and performance. It helps to make the quantitative judgment about financial positions and performance of a firm.

There are various types of ratios that can be used to analyze the financial performance of the firm. Here, in this research only the relevant ratios are used to find the financial position of ADBL, RBBL and NBL.

i) Liquidity Ratio

Liquidity refers to the ability of a firm to meet its short term obligations. Liquidity ratios measure the short term solvency or liquidity position of a firm. It reflects the short term financial strength of the business. In order to ensure short term solvency, the company must maintain required liquidity ratio. But if the entire amount is invested in liquid assets, it will result bad credit rating, less creditors' confidence, eventually may lead to bankruptcy. Thus, the company should endeavor to maintain proper balance between inadequate liquidity and unnecessary liquidity for the survival and avoiding risk.

a. Current Ratio

The current ratio shows the relationship between current assets and the current liabilities. It is calculated by dividing total current assets by total current liabilities.

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Assets that can be converted into cash within one year period are called current assets. It includes cash and bank balance, investment in treasury bills, loans and advances, bills receivables, account receivables, prepaid expenses, etc.

Current liabilities are those liabilities which are to be paid normally within a year. It includes bills payable, tax payable, dividend payable, bank overdraft, accrued expenses, short term bank loan, etc.

The current ratio of 2:1 is regarded as the satisfactory ratio.

b. Cash and Bank Balance to Current and Saving Deposit Ratio

The bank should maintain adequate cash and bank balance to meet the unexpected and heavy withdrawal of deposits. So this ratio measures the ability of the bank to meet its immediate obligations.

Cash and bank balance consists of cash in hand, foreign cash in hand, cheques and balance with domestic and foreign banks. Likewise, a current and saving deposit includes all types of deposits except fixed deposit.

Cash and bank balance to current and saving deposit ratio is calculated by dividing cash and bank balance by current and saving deposits as under

$$\text{Cash and Bank Balance to Current and Saving Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash \& Bank Balance}}{\text{Current \& Saving Deposit}}$$

This ratio shows the bank's ability to meet its immediate obligations. Higher the ratio shows the higher liquidity position and the ability to cover the deposit and vice-versa.

c. Cash and Bank Balance to Total Deposit Ratio

Cash and bank balances are the most liquid current assets. This ratio measure percentage of most liquid fund with the bank to make immediate payment to depositors. This ratio is computed by dividing cash and bank balances by total deposit.

$$\text{Cash and Bank Balance to Total Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash and Bank Balance}}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

Cash and bank balance includes cash on hand, foreign cash on hand, balance with Nepal Rastra Bank, balance with domestic banks, balance held in foreign banks and other financial institutions. The total deposits encompass current deposits, fixed deposits and saving deposits. A high ratio indicates the greater ability to meet their deposits liability and vice versa. Moreover, too high ratio is unfavorable, as capital will be tied-up and opportunity cost will be higher.

ii) Leverage Ratio

This ratio is also called solvency ratio or capital structure ratio. A firm should have strong short-term as well as long-term financial position. To judge the long term financial position of the firm, these ratios help to measure the financial contribution of owners and creditors comparatively. These ratios indicate the situation of the capital structure, which is calculated to measure the company's ability of using debt for benefit of shareholders. Long-term creditors like debenture holders, financial institutions are more interested to the firm's long term financial health, debt servicing capacity and strength and weakness of the concerns. This ratio may be calculated from the balance sheet items to determine the proportion of debt in total financing. In summary debt ratio tell us the relative proportions of capital contribution by creditors and by owner.

a. Debt Assets Ratio

This ratio exhibits the relationship between creditors fund and owners capital. This ratio shows the proportion of outside fund used in financing total assets. It also provides security /financial safety to the outsider's i.e. Potential shareholder, depositor or investors. Higher debt ratio indicates higher financial risk as well as increasing claims of outsiders in total assets and lower ratio indicates lower financial risk as well as decreasing claims of outsider over the total assets of the firm. Generally 1:2 ratios are considered good but however no hard and fast rule is prescribed. This ratio is representing as follows:

$$\text{Debt Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

b. Debt Equity Ratio

Debt equity ratio examines the relative claims of creditors and owners against the firm assets. Alternatively, the debt equity ratio indicates the combinations of debt capital and equity capital fund to the total investment. The ratio is computed by using following formula:

$$\text{Debt Equity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$$

c. Equity to Total Assets Ratio

This ratio shows the proportion of equity capital in the total assets. Equity is the main source of capital. Ratio of equity capital in the capital structure differs from company to company. It is calculated by dividing Equity by total assets as under:

$$\text{Equity to Total Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Equity}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

d. Interest Coverage Ratio

This ratio measures how much net income before interest and taxes could decline and still provide coverage of total interest expenses. It is sometimes called as debt service ratio. This ratio emphasizes the ability of the firm to generate enough income to cover interest expenses. This ratio is directly connected to the ability of the firm to pay interest (Munankarmi, 2002: 470). This ratio is obtained by dividing net profit before deduction and interest and tax by interest charge as follows.

$$\text{Interest Coverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Profit before deduction of Interest \& Tax}}{\text{Total Interest}}$$

This ratio indicates the ability of bank to pay interest out of its profits. It also indicates the extent to which the profits of the company may decrease without in any way affecting its ability to meet its interest obligations. Higher ratio is desirable but too high ratio indicates the firm is very conservative in using debt. A lower ratio indicates excessive use of debt or insufficient operation.

iii) Profitability Ratio

Profit is the difference between total revenues and total expenses over a period of time. Profit is the ultimate output of a commercial bank and it will have no future if it fails to make sufficient profits. Therefore, the financial manager continuously evaluates the efficiency of the banks in terms of profits. Profitability shows the overall efficiency of the business concerns. The relation of the return of the firm to either its sales or equity of its assets is known as profitability ratio. Profit is necessary to survive in any business field for its successful operation and further expansion. It measures management's overall effectiveness as shown by the return generated on sales and investment. Higher the profitability ratio, better the financial performance of the bank and vice-versa. Profitability ratio can be calculated by following different ratio:

a. Return on Total Assets

Return refers the profit after interest and taxes. It is also known as Net Profit on Total Assets. This ratio evaluates the efficiency of company in utilizing and mobilizing of assets and its survival. It is useful for measurement of the profitability of all financial resources invested in the bank assets. It also provides the foundation necessary for company to deliver a good return on equity. Higher Return on Assets (ROA) indicates

higher efficiency in utilization of total assets and vice-versa. ROA is calculated by dividing the amount of net profit by the total assets.

$$\text{Return on Total Assets} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

b. Net Profit to Total deposits

Net profit to total deposit ratio evaluate whether management has been capable to mobilizes and utilize the deposit. It also helps to know the overall performance and generation of profit of Bank. This ratio is most important to identify whether the organization well efficient or not in mobilizing its total deposits. So that corrective action could be taken. Higher ratio indicates better utilization of deposit and vice-versa. Here net profit is profit after taxes and total deposit means total amount of deposit in various account i.e. saving, current, fixed and other. The return on total deposits ratio can be computed by dividing net profit by total deposit This can be express as follows:

$$\text{Net Profit to Total Deposits} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

c. Staff Expenses to Total Income

Staff expenses include the salary and allowances contribution to provident fund and gratuity fund, staff training expenses and other allowances and expenses made to staff. It measures the proportion of income spent for the staff, whose contribution is great significance in the success of the bank

This ratio is calculated by dividing staff expenses by total income as follows:

$$\text{Staff Expenses to Total Income Ratio} = \frac{\text{Staff Expenses}}{\text{Total Income}}$$

d. Interest Earned to Total Assets

The ratio shows the earning capacity of a Bank on its total assets (working fund). This ratio exhibits the extent on which Banks are successful in mobilizing their working funds to generate income as much as possible.

The higher ratio will indicate the high earning power of the banks on its total assets. Total interest earned is calculated by adding the total interest income from loans and advances, cash credit, overdrafts and government securities etc. This ratio is calculated by dividing net profit by total assets.

$$\text{Interest Earned to Total Assets} = \frac{\text{Interest Earned}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

Activity / Assets Management Ratio

Activity ratio evaluates the efficiency with which the firm manages and utilizes its assets. This ratio is also known as turnover ratio. It measures how effectively the company employs the resources at its command. Funds are created by the collection of share as well as debt from the owner, creditors and outside parties. Those funds are invested in procuring various kinds of assets to generate profits or income.

Activity ratios are the indicators of a concern banks with regard to its efficiency in assets management, hence they are often referred to as efficiency ratio. They are computed to assess the company's efficiency in utilizing available resource.

a. Loan Advances to Total Deposit Ratio

This ratio measures the extent to which the banks are successful to utilize the outsiders fund (Total deposit) for the profit generating purpose on the loans and advance. Generally, a high ratio reflects higher efficiency to the utilization of fund and vice-versa. It can be calculated by dividing the amount of loans and advances by the amount of total deposits, which is given as below:

$$\text{Loan and Advances to Total Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Loans and Advances}}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

Here loan and advances refers to total of loan, advances and overdraft and total deposits refer to total of all kinds of deposit.

b. Loan and Advances to Fixed Deposit Ratio

This ratio indicates how many times the amount is used in loans and advances in comparison to fixed deposits. Fixed Deposits are the main source of deposit of bank and are high interest bearing obligation whereas loans and advances are the major sources of investment to generate income for the commercial banks. This ratio is calculated by dividing the amount of loans and advances by fixed deposits that is given below:

$$\text{Loan and Advances to Fixed Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Loans and Advances}}{\text{Fixed Deposit}}$$

c. Loan and Advances to Saving Deposit Ratio

Loans and advances to saving deposits ratio indicates how much saving deposits are used as loans and advances by the individual banks. Saving deposits are low interest bearing and are also most liquid form of liabilities. So this ratio should be maintained with due consideration. Too high ratio indicates most of the deposit is invested and it

will be difficult for the banks to make the payment to the customers. Similarly, too low ratio also indicates idle cash in the bank.

$$\text{Loans and Advances to Saving Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Loans and Advances}}{\text{Saving Deposit}}$$

d. Total Investment to Total Deposit Ratio

Investment is one of the major forms of credit created to earn income. This implies the utilization of firm's deposit on investment in government securities and share, debenture of the other companies and banks. This ratio measure the extent to which the bank are successful in mobilizing total investment on the total deposits. The amount of deposits should be soundly invested as the bank has to provide interest on its deposits and also has to declared a handsome dividend to its owners and shareholders. This ratio can be calculated by dividing total investment by total deposit. This ratio is mention as below:

$$\text{Total Investment to Total Deposit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Investment}}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

Investment consist of investment of government securities, investment on debenture and bonds, shares in subsidiary companies, share in other companies and other investment. A high ratio indicates that the Bank's efficiency is more in investing on its deposit and low ratio indicate inability to put its deposits for the lending activities.

iv) Growth Ratio

Growth ratio represents how well the banks are maintaining their economic and financial position. A high ratio generally indicates better performance and vice-versa. To examine and analyze the expansion and growth of company, following growth ratio are calculated in this study.

3.6.2 Statistical Tools:

Statistical tools are the mathematical techniques used to analyze and interpret performance. It is used to describe the relationship between variables and interpret the result. Statistics is also used to test the hypothesis that is set to know the information of population.

a) Mean (\bar{X}):

The arithmetic mean or average is the sum of total values to the number of observations in the sample. It represents the entire data which lies almost between the two extremes. For this reason, an average is frequently referred to as a measure of central tendency. In

this study it is used in data related to deposits, loans and advances and net profit of sample banks over five years.

It is calculated as: $\text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of Total Values}}{\text{No. of values}}$

b) Standard Deviation (S.D.):

S.D. is an absolute measure of dispersion in which the drawbacks present in other measures of dispersion are removed. It is said to be the best measure of dispersion as it satisfies most of the requisites of a good measures of dispersion. The measurement of the scatterings of the mass of figures in a series about an average is known as dispersion. The high amount of dispersion reflects high standard deviation. The small standard deviation means the high degree of homogeneity of the observations. In simple term high SD means very less similarity in the values and low SD means high similarity among the values. SD gives the accurate result between the values only if their mean are same. In case of different mean, SD cannot be the accurate result. SD is the positive square root of the arithmetic mean of the square of deviation of items taken from arithmetic mean. It is denoted by:

$$(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})^2}{N}}$$

c) Coefficient of Variation (CV):

CV reflects the relation between standard deviation and mean. The relative measure of dispersion based on the standard deviation is known as coefficient of standard deviation. The coefficient of dispersion based on standard deviation multiplied by 100 is known as C.V. It is used for comparing variability of two distributions. If the \bar{X} be the arithmetic mean and σ be the standard deviation of the distribution, then the C.V. is defined as,

$$\text{C.V.} = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{X}} \times 100\%$$

Lesser the C.V. more will be the uniformity; consistency and more the C.V. less will be the uniformity and consistency.

d) Coefficient of Correlation (r):

Correlation Analysis is the statistical tools that we can use to describe the degree to which one variable is linearly related to another. Coefficient of Correlation is the measurement of the degree of positive and negative relationship between two casually

related sets of figures. Its value lies somewhere ranging between -1 to +1. If both variables are constantly changing in the similar direction, the value of coefficient will be +1 indicating perfect positive correlation. When the value coefficient will be -1 two variables take place in opposite direction. The correlation is said to be perfect negative. In this study, simple coefficient of correlation is used to examine the relationship of different factors with deposits and other variables. The data regarding deposits over different years are tabulated and their relationship with each other is drawn out. In practical life, the possibility of obtaining either perfect positive or perfect negative correlation is very rare. Mathematically it is expressed as:

$$\text{Coefficient of Correlation}(r) = \frac{\text{Cov}(XY)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \quad r = \frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{(N-1)\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

$$\text{Or, } r = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

Where, σ_x , σ_y are the standard deviation of the distributions of X and Y values respectively.

$$\text{Cov}(X, Y) = \text{Co variation of X, Y, value} = \frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{(N-1)}$$

e) Coefficient of Determination (r^2):

The coefficient of determination is the measure of the degree of linear association or correlation between two or more independent variables. It measures the percentage total variation in dependent variables explained by independent variables. If r^2 has a zero value then, it indicates that there is no correlation which means all the data points in scatter diagram fall exactly on the regression line. If it has the value equal to one then it indicates that there is perfect correlation and as such the regression line is the perfect estimator. But in most of the cases the value of r^2 will lie somewhere between these two extremes of 1 and 0. One should remember that r^2 close to 1 indicates a strong correlation between two variables and r^2 near to 0 means there is little correlation.

Coefficient of Determination (r^2)

$$\text{Coefficient of Determination } (r^2) = \frac{\text{Explained Variation}}{\text{Total Variation}}$$

$$\text{Or, } r^2 = \frac{1 - \text{Unexplained Variation}}{\text{Total Variation}}$$

f) Probable Error

The Probable Error (PE) of correlation coefficient is an old measure of testing of reliability of an observed correlation coefficient. The Probable Error of the correlation coefficient is the basis for the interpretation of its value. PE is used in interpretation whether the calculated value of r is significant or not.

- If $r < PE$ then it is insignificant or there is no evidence of correlation.
- If $r > 6PE$ then, it is significant.
- If $PE < r < 6PE$ then, nothing can be concluded.

g) Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is the development of the statistical model that can be used to predict the values of variable. There are two types of variable in regression analysis. The variable whose value is to be predicted is called dependent variable and the variable which is used for prediction is called independent variable. The dependent variable is based upon the value of independent variable. The simple linear regression analysis would be $Y = a + bX$

Where, Y is the dependent variable, X is the independent variable

a is the average value of Y when X equals zero

b is the expected change in Y per unit change in X

h) Trend Analysis:

The Arrangement of Statistical data chronologically (according to occurrence of time) is known as time series and the statistical analysis of this chronological variation is termed as Trend Analysis. It helps to know the past behavior of data in certain span of time interval. On the basis of these past trends, one can make plan in forthcoming days. This Least square method is the most popular and widely used mathematical method of measuring trend. This is frequently used for future prediction. There are various types of curves that may be used to describe the given data but in this text, an attempt has been made to discuss only the fitting of linear trend by the least square method.

Let, the equation of Trend Analysis would be,

$$Y = a + bx$$

Where, Y = the given value of the variable in time series. It is a dependent variable.

a = Intercept of trend line or y -intercept.

b = Slope of Trend Line.

x = Time Variable

3.7 Research Framework

From the earlier established research works conducted on fund management and its impact in the financial performance of commercial banks, it is obvious that this field of research is very important in the development of modern security market. This study has been undertaken to identify the major factors that determine the financial performance of the commercial banks.

In relation to this, there is a call to conduct a research to understand whether the independent variables deposit, credit, profit and non-performing loan affect the financial performance of the commercial bank. The schematic diagram below shows the relationship between dependent and independent variables presented in figure 3.1

Figure 3.1: Research Framework of the study

3.7.1 Explanation of dependent and independent variables

The financial performance of the commercial banks is dependent variables. It is dependent on other variables. Some independent variables are deposit, Credit, Profit and non-performing loan. The details explanation of the variables are as follows.

a) Deposit

A deposit is a financial term that means money held at a bank. A deposit is a transaction involving a transfer of money to another party for safekeeping. However, a deposit can refer to a portion of money used as security or collateral for the delivery of a good. Financial performance is directly depended on the deposit. Banks having higher deposit can lend to customer and earns profit.

Credit

Credit is generally defined as a contract agreement in which a borrower receives a sum of money or something of value and repays the lender at a later date, generally with interest. Credit also may refer to the creditworthiness or credit history of an individual or a company. To an accountant, it often refers to a bookkeeping entry that either decreases assets or increases liabilities and equity on a company's balance sheet. Credit is also the factor which determine the financial performance of the commercial banks. Banks with higher loan (credit) earns much profit which is the major parameter of financial performance in this century.

b) Profit

Profit describes the financial benefit realized when revenue generated from a business activity exceeds the expenses, costs, and taxes involved in sustaining the activity in question. Any profits earned funnel back to business owners, who choose to either pocket the cash, distribute it to shareholders as dividends, or reinvest it back into the business. There is huge competition in the market for achieving high profit which is also a parameter of financial performance.

d) Non- Performing Loan

A non-performing loan (NPL) is a loan in which the borrower is in default and has not paid the monthly principal and interest repayments for a specified period. Non-performing loans occur when borrowers run out of money to make repayments or get into situations that make it difficult for them to continue making repayments towards the loan. This is negative relationship between non-performing loan and financial performance of the commercial banks. Low non-performing loan indicates the better financial performance and vice-versa.

e) Financial Performance

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period. Financial performance of the commercial banks is dependent with many other factors.

CHAPTER IV

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this chapter is to carry out secondary data analysis. In this chapter, the relevant data and information regarding the ratios of the commercial banks are presented and analyzed comparatively. The financial as well as statistical tools are used for the comparison of the financial indicators. Also the correlation and regression analysis of the sample firm is calculated and data are presented in a systematic tabulated form.

Present chapter will discuss the various aspects of financial aspect of sample commercial banks and their actual output so that recommendation can be given for remedial purposes. Analysis is done to portrait the financial figures in tabular or in graphical form.

4.1 Analysis of Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial banks

High proportion of loans and advances indicates the good position of the organization indicating good mobilization of deposits of funds. Low proportion of loan indicates no use of fund properly. Loan is the risky assets. Higher loans and advances to total assets ratio shows high risk and inversely low loans and advances to total assets ratio shows low risk.

4.1.1 Loan and Advances of Rastriya Banijya Bank (RBB).

Loans and advances means bills discounted, overdraft, leasing, export bills purchased, other bills received or purchased, import bills, customer's liability for acceptances, drawings against un cleared effects, encashment of cheques drawn against other branches or offices where the drawer's current account has insufficient cleared and withdrawable balance or against other banks, or any other credit extended to a person by a bank or financial institution, and it excludes the undrawn or un availed balance of any line of credit; It means any direct or indirect advance of funds (including obligations as maker or endorser arising from discounting of commercial/business paper) which are made to a person on the basis of an obligation to repay the funds. "Loans and advances" also includes all exposures as defined in the Act.

While disbursing deposit as loan and advance banks must act prudently. Banks deals with many people known as its clients in the form of depositor, creditor and other stake holders. Meantime bank cannot preserve deposit without using as loan and advances because they are obliged to meet the interest of deposit.

Table No.4.1
Analysis of Loan and Advances of RBB (In Crore)

Year	Loan and Advances	Change (%)
2011/12	3045	-
2012/13	4905	61.08
2013/14	6085	24.06
2014/15	7584	24.63
2015/16	8547	12.70
2016/17	10643	24.52
2017/18	12087	13.57
2018/19	14812	22.54
2019/20	15652	5.67
2020/21	19597	25.20
Mean	10295.70	23.77%
S.D	5256.78	15.62%
Minimum	3045.00	5.67%
Maximum	19597.00	61.08%
C.V	0.51	0.66

Source: Audited Report of RBB

Table no. 4.1 shows the total loan and advances position of RBB from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The increment of loan and advances of RBB is positive in all F/Y. The highest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2012/13 i.e.61.08% and lowest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2019/20 i.e. 5.67%.

The average loan of RBB during analysis period is Rs.10295.70 crore. The standard deviation of loan of RBB is 5268.78. The maximum loan amount disbursed by RBB is Rs. 19597 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum loan amount is Rs.3045 crores in F/Y 2011/12. The average loan increment is 23.77 %. The standard deviation of loan increment is 15.62%. Similarly, the minimum increment in loan is 5.67% whereas the maximum loan increment is 61.08%.

There is positive increment in loan and advances of RBB during the analysis period. The C.V of 0.51 shows that 0.51unit of risk must be taken to disburse the one percent of average loan.

4.1.2 Loan and Advances of Agricultural Development Bank Limited (ADBL)

High proportion of loans indicates the good position of the organization indicating good mobilization of deposits of funds. Low proportion of loan indicates no use of fund properly. Loan is risky assets. The loan & advances of ADBL can be presented in following table.

Table No.4.2
Analysis of Loan and Advances of ADBL (In Crore)

Year	Loan and Advances	Change (%)
2011/12	4498.84	-
2012/13	5491.85	22.07%
2013/14	6247.29	13.76%
2014/15	7223.85	15.63%
2015/16	8341.83	15.48%
2016/17	9770.31	17.12%
2017/18	10398.72	6.43%
2018/19	11175.02	7.47%
2019/20	12337.71	10.40%
2020/21	15147.07	22.77%
Mean	9063.25	14.57%
S.D	3331.67	5.77%
Minimum	4498.84	6.43%
Maximum	15147.07	22.77%
C.V	0.37	0.40

Source: Audit Report of ADBL

Table no. 4.2 shows the total loan and advances position of ADBL from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The highest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2020/21 i.e.22.77% and lowest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2017/18 i.e. 6.43%. The average loan of ADBL during analysis period is Rs.9063.25 crore. The standard deviation of loan of ADBL is 3331.67.

The maximum loan amount disbursed by ADBL is Rs.15147.07 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum loan amount is Rs.3331.67 crores in F/Y 2011/12. The average loan increment is 14.57 %. Similarly, the minimum increment in loan is 5.67% whereas the maximum loan increment is 61.08%. There is positive increment in loan and advances of ADBL during the analysis period.

4.1.3 Loan and Advances of Nepal Bank Limited (NBL)

Commercial banks are the major source of credit for business firms and households in many countries. NPA of banks is an important criterion to assess the financial health of banking sector (Ahmed, 2000), identification of the potential problem and close monitoring is paramount importance for the better performance of this sector.

Table No.4.3
Analysis of Loan and Advances of NBL (In Crore)

Year	Loan and Advances	Change (%)
2011/12	2969.90	-
2012/13	3785.20	27.45%
2013/14	4121.80	8.89%
2014/15	5338.80	29.53%
2015/16	6352.40	18.99%
2016/17	7318.60	15.21%
2017/18	7829.60	6.98%
2018/19	9572.50	22.26%
2019/20	10683.00	11.60%
2020/21	14195.91	32.88%
Mean	7216.77	19.31%
S.D	3501.16	9.36%
Minimum	2969.90	6.98%
Maximum	14195.91	32.88%
C.V	0.49	0.48

Source: Annual Report of NBL

Table no. 4.3 shows the total loan and advances position of NBL from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The highest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2020/21 i.e.32.88% and lowest increment in loan and advances is in F/Y 2017/18 i.e. 6.98%. The average loan of NBL during analysis period is Rs.7216.77crores. The standard deviation of loan of NBL is 3501.16. The maximum loan amount disbursed by NBL is Rs.14195.91 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum loan amount is Rs.2969.90 crores in F/Y 2011/12.

The average loan increment is 19.31 %. Similarly, the minimum increment in loan is 6.98% whereas the maximum loan increment is 32.88%. There is positive increment in loan and advances of NBL during the analysis period.

4.1.4 Comparative analysis of Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial Banks.

Loan and advances are the most profitable of all assets of the bank. This asset constitutes primary sources of income to bank. They are also the least liquid form of asset of the bank. Loan and advances may take different forms and are allowed against various types of securities. Granting loan and advances always carries certain degree of risk. The comparative loan and advances of sample commercial banks can be presented as below.

Table No.4.4
Comparative analysis of Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial Banks

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	3045	4498.84	2969.90
2012/13	4905	5491.85	3785.20
2013/14	6085	6247.29	4121.80
2014/15	7584	7223.85	5338.80
2015/16	8547	8341.83	6352.40
2016/17	10643	9770.31	7318.60
2017/18	12087	10398.72	7829.60
2018/19	14812	11175.02	9572.50
2019/20	15652	12337.71	10683.00
2020/21	19597	15147.07	14195.91
Mean	10295.70	9063.25	7216.77
S.D	5256.78	3331.67	3501.16
Minimum	3045.00	4498.84	2969.90
Maximum	19597.00	15147.07	14195.91
C.V	0.51	0.37	0.49

Source: Audit Report of Sample Commercial Banks

Figure No. 4.1 Analysis of Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial Banks

Table no.4.4 and figure no. 4.1 shows the comparative analysis of total loan and advances position of sample commercial banks from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The average loan disbursement of RBB is greater than all commercial banks and NBL is lower than all commercial banks during analysis period.

The total loan and disbursement of RBB is highest in all F/Y and NBL has lowest loan disbursement in the entire period. NBL has lowest amount of loan in 2011/12 i.e.2969.90 crores but it has aggressively disbursed highest loan in succeeding F/Y. It shows that RBB is has good performance in granting loan to its valued customers.

The loan and advances of ADBL is greater than RBB and NBL in the starting F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2013/14. The loan and advances of RBB is highest in all F/Y from F/Y 2014/15. The loan and advances of NBL is lower than ADBL and NBL in all F/Y.

The financial performance of RBB is greater than NBL and ADBL according to the loan disbursed. From the disbursed, RBB can collect highest amount of interest income, a major parameter of profit of the company.

4.2 Analysis of Deposit of Sample Commercial Banks

Deposit refers to the money an investor transfers into a savings or checking account held at a bank or credit union. The money deposited still belongs to the person or entity that deposited the money, and that person or entity can withdraw the money at any time, transfer it to another person's account, or use the money to purchase goods.

4.2.1 Analysis of Deposit of RBB

A deposit is a financial term that means money held at a bank. A deposit is a transaction involving a transfer of money to another party for safekeeping. When an individual deposits money into a banking account, it earns interest.

Table No.4.5
Analysis of Deposit of RBB (In Crores)

Year	Deposit	Change (%)
2011/12	8778	-
2012/13	9109	3.77%
2013/14	10727	17.76%
2014/15	12422	15.80%
2015/16	14621	17.70%
2016/17	15358	5.04%
2017/18	16933	10.26%
2018/19	19199	13.38%
2019/20	23298	21.35%
2020/21	26620	14.26%
Mean	15706.50	13.26%
S.D	5952.14	5.91%
Minimum	8778.00	3.77%
Maximum	26620.00	21.35%
C.V	0.38	0.45

Source: Annual Report of RBB

Table no. 4.5 shows the total deposit of RBB from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The highest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2019/20 i.e.21.35% and lowest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2011/12 i.e. 3.77%. The average deposit of RBB during analysis period is Rs.15706.50 crore. The standard deviation of deposit of RBB is 5952.14. The maximum deposit amount collected by RBB is Rs.26620 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum deposit amount is Rs.8778 crores in F/Y 2011/12. The average deposit increment is 13.26%. There is positive increment in deposit of RBB during the analysis period.

4.2.2 Analysis of Deposit of ADBL

Deposit is a term used to denote the money kept or held in any bank account, especially to accumulate interest. The fund used as a security to get the goods delivered can also be called a deposit. Any transaction processed to transfer money to an entity for safeguarding can be referred to as a deposit.

Table No.4.6
Analysis of Deposit of ADBL (In Crores)

Year	Deposit	Change (%)
2011/12	4326.41	-
2012/13	5447.76	25.92%
2013/14	6589.84	20.96%
2014/15	7703.50	16.90%
2015/16	8738.70	13.44%
2016/17	9981.60	14.22%
2017/18	10473.10	4.92%
2018/19	11936.30	13.97%
2019/20	14373.20	20.42%
2020/21	16299.00	13.40%
Mean	9586.94	16.02%
S.D	3836.61	5.99%
Minimum	4326.41	4.92%
Maximum	16299.00	25.92%
C.V	0.40	0.37

Source: Annual Report of ADBL

Table no. 4.6 shows the total deposit of ADBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The highest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2012/13 i.e.25.92% and lowest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2017/18 i.e. 4.92%. The average deposit of ADBL during analysis period is Rs.9586.94 crore. The standard deviation of deposit of ADBL is 3836.61.

The maximum deposit amount collected by ADBL is Rs.16299 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum deposit amount is Rs.4326.41 crores in F/Y 2011/12. The average deposit increment is 16.02%. There is positive increment in deposit of ADBL during the analysis period.

4.2.3 Analysis of Deposit of NBL

Deposit account is a bank account maintained by a financial institution in which a customer can deposit and withdraw money. Deposit accounts can be savings accounts, current accounts or any of several other types of accounts. Transactions on deposit accounts are recorded in a bank's books, and the resulting balance is recorded as a liability of the bank and represents an amount owed by the bank to the customer. In other words, the banker-customer (depositor) relationship is one of debtor-creditor.

Table No.4.7

Analysis of Deposit of NBL (In Crores)

Year	Deposit	Change (%)
2011/12	5605.20	-
2012/13	6298.40	12.37%
2013/14	6933.80	10.09%
2014/15	7799.99	12.49%
2015/16	8941.00	14.63%
2016/17	9394.40	5.07%
2017/18	9983.10	6.27%
2018/19	11827.5	18.48%
2019/20	14298.90	20.90%
2020/21	16362.30	14.43%
Mean	9744.46	12.75%
S.D	3502.26	5.17%
Minimum	5605.20	5.07%
Maximum	16362.30	20.90%
C.V	0.36	0.41

Source: Annual Report of NBL

Table no. 4.7 shows the total deposit of NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The highest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2019/20 i.e.20.90% and lowest increment in deposit is in F/Y 2016/17 i.e. 5.07%. The average deposit of NBL during analysis period is Rs.9744.46 crore.

The standard deviation of deposit of NBL is 3502.26. The maximum deposit amount collected by NBL is Rs.16362 crores in F/Y2020/21 and minimum deposit amount is Rs.5605.20 crores in F/Y 2011/12. The average deposit increment is 12.75%. There is positive increment in deposit of NBL during the analysis period.

4.2.4 Comparative analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks.

A deposit account in which amounts over a certain balance are automatically transferred to another account pursuant to a pre-determined set of arrangements. A deposit account that allows for the withdrawal of funds without penalty but requires a higher minimum balance to earn interest.

Table No.4.8

Comparative analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks (crores)			
Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	8778	4326.41	5605.20
2012/13	9109	5447.76	6298.40
2013/14	10727	6589.84	6933.80
2014/15	12422	7703.50	7799.99
2015/16	14621	8738.70	8941.00
2016/17	15358	9981.60	9394.40
2017/18	16933	10473.10	9983.10
2018/19	19199	11936.30	11827.5
2019/20	23298	14373.20	14298.90
2020/21	26620	16299.00	16362.30
Mean	15706.50	9586.94	9744.46
S.D	5952.14	3836.61	3502.26
Minimum	8778.00	4326.41	5605.20
Maximum	26620.00	16299.00	16362.30
C.V	0.38	0.40	0.36

Source: Audit Report of Sample Commercial Banks

Figure No.4.2 analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks (crores)

Table no. 4.8 and figure no. 4.2 shows the comparative analysis of total deposit position of sample commercial banks from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The average deposit of RBB is greater than all commercial banks and NBL is lower than all commercial banks during analysis period. The average deposit of RBB is highest than ADBL and NBL during analysis period. Similarly, NBL is following to RBB in collecting deposit rather than ADBL.

The total deposit of RBB is highest in all F/Y and NBL has lowest deposit collected in the entire period. ADBL has lowest amount of loan in 2011/12 i.e.4326.41 crores but it has aggressively collected highest deposit in succeeding F/Y. It shows that RBB is has good performance in collecting deposit from its valued customers.

From Figure no., the deposit amount collected by the RBB is greater than ADBL and NBL. The deposit of NBL and ADBL is almost same in every F/Y.

According to the deposit collected, the financial performance of RBB is good than ADBL and NBL. From the deposit collected, it can grant the loan to its valued customers.

4.3 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial banks

NPL is defined as a loan that is not earning income or full payment of principal and interest is no longer anticipated, principal or interest is 90 days or more delinquent, or the maturity date has passed and payment in full has not been made. It is a loan of

which the borrower has failed to make the agreed upon scheduled payments based on the loan agreement.

4.3.1 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of RBB

NPL to total loan measures the credit risk of bank. Higher the ratio indicates high coverage of NPL on total loan, indicates high credit risk, which may affect sustainability of the bank.

Table No.4.9
Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of RBB (In %)

Year	Total Loan	NPL (%)	Change (%)
2011/12	3045	7.27	-
2012/13	4905	5.32	-26.82%
2013/14	6085	6.38	19.92%
2014/15	7584	5.35	-16.14%
2015/16	8547	4.25	-20.56%
2016/17	10643	3.77	-11.29%
2017/18	12087	4.75	25.99%
2018/19	14812	4.59	-3.37%
2019/20	15652	4.08	-11.11%
2020/21	19597	3.23	-20.83%
Mean	10295.70	4.90	-7.13%
S.D	5256.78	1.22	18.42%
Minimum	3045.00	3.23	-26.82%
Maximum	19597.00	7.27	25.99%
C.V	0.51	0.25	-2.58

Source: Audit Report of RBB

Table no. 4.9 shows the ratio of NPL to total loan and advances of RBB from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The ratio of NPL to total loans and advances is decreasing in all F/Y except on F/Y 2013/14 and F/Y2017/18. The average NPL is 4.90 % and NPL is 3.23%in F/Y 2020/21.RBB is successful in declining the NPL from 7.27% to 3.23%. There is negative relationship between total loan and advances and NPL of RBB during period.

4.3.2 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of ADBL

A loan that is nearing a default or is already defaulted is referred to as a non-performing loan. After the loan reaches the non- performing state, the probability of its repayment

reduces significantly. Though it depends on the terms of the contract, a loan classified as non-performing when the interest payment as well as principal payments are overdue by more than 90 days.

Table No.4.10
Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of ADBL (In %)

Year	Total Loan	NPL (%)	Change (%)
2011/12	4498.84	8.98	-
2012/13	5491.85	5.85	-34.86%
2013/14	6247.29	5.46	-6.67%
2014/15	7223.85	5.35	-2.01%
2015/16	8341.83	4.36	-18.50%
2016/17	9770.31	4.60	5.50%
2017/18	10398.72	3.50	-23.91%
2018/19	11175.02	3.29	-6.00%
2019/20	12337.71	2.84	-13.68%
2020/21	15147.07	1.88	-33.80%
Mean	9063.25	4.61	-14.88%
S.D	3331.67	1.99	14.06%
Minimum	4498.84	1.88	-34.86%
Maximum	15147.07	8.98	5.50%
C.V	0.37	0.43	-0.94

Source: Audit Report of ADBL

Table no. 4.10 shows the ratio of NPL to total loan and advances of ADBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The ratio of NPL to total loans and advances is decreasing in all F/Y except on F/Y 2017/18.

The average NPL is 4.61% and NPL is 1.88% in F/Y 2020/21. ADBL is successful in declining the NPL from 8.98% to 1.88%. The NPL percent of ADBL is gradually declining from the analysis period and is success to place NPL in below 2 percent. There is negative relationship between total loan and advances and NPL of ADBL during analysis period.

4.3.3 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of NBL

A loan that is nearing a default or is already defaulted is referred to as a non-performing loan. After the loan reaches the non-performing state, the probability of its repayment

reduces significantly. Though it depends on the terms of the contract, a loan classified as non-performing when the interest payment as well as principal payments are overdue by more than 90 days.

Table No.4.11
Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of NBL (In %)

Year	Total Loan	NPL (%)	Change (%)
2011/12	2969.90	5.58	-
2012/13	3785.20	5.24	-6.09%
2013/14	4121.80	5.12	-2.29%
2014/15	5338.80	3.98	-22.27%
2015/16	6352.40	3.11	-21.86%
2016/17	7318.60	3.32	6.75%
2017/18	7829.60	3.37	1.51%
2018/19	9572.50	2.64	-21.66%
2019/20	10683.00	2.47	-6.44%
2020/21	14195.91	2.05	-17.00%
Mean	7216.77	3.69	-9.93%
S.D	3501.16	1.25	11.05%
Minimum	2969.90	2.05	-22.27%
Maximum	14195.91	5.58	6.75%
C.V	0.49	0.34	-1.11

Source: Audit Report of NBL

Table no. 4.11 shows the ratio of NPL to total loan and advances of NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. The ratio of NPL to total loans and advances is decreasing in all F/Y except on F/Y 2016/17 and 2017/18.

The average NPL is 3.69% and NPL is 2.05% in F/Y 2020/21. NBL is successful in declining the NPL from 5.58% to 2.05%. The NPL percent of NBL is gradually declining from the analysis period and is success to place NPL in 2 percent.

There is negative relationship between total loan and advances and NPL of NBL during analysis period. NPL is declining in linear form from the analysis period.

4.3.4 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial Banks

Commercial banks collect money from depositors in small amount to huge amount and disbursed to borrowers as loan & advances as capital for business enterprises. So,

repayment of loan and advances to banks depends upon the economic and financial health of these enterprises. The NPL of sample commercial banks are presented as below table.

Table No.4.12

Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of sample commercial bank (In %)			
Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	7.27	8.98	5.58
2012/13	5.32	5.85	5.24
2013/14	6.38	5.46	5.12
2014/15	5.35	5.35	3.98
2015/16	4.25	4.36	3.11
2016/17	3.77	4.60	3.32
2017/18	4.75	3.50	3.37
2018/19	4.59	3.29	2.64
2019/20	4.08	2.84	2.47
2020/21	3.23	1.88	2.05
Mean	4.90	4.61	3.69
S.D	1.22	1.99	1.25
Minimum	3.23	1.88	2.05
Maximum	7.27	8.98	5.58
C.V	0.25	0.43	0.34

Source: Audit Report of Sample Commercial Banks

Figure 4.3 Analysis of NPL to Loan and Advances of sample commercial banks

Table no. 4.12 and figure no. 4.3 shows the NPL position of sample commercial banks. ADBL has highest i.e. 8.98% and NBL has lowest 5.58% NPL in 2011/12. RBB has highest and ADBL has lowest NPL in 2020/21. Similarly, RBB has highest and NBL has lowest NPL in average during analysis period. ADBL and NBL has lowest NPL in comparison to RBB. There is highest NPL in RBB and NBL in comparison to other ADBL.

From the above figure, the NPL of all sample commercial banks are decreasing from the analysis period. In the beginning of starting F/Y NPL of ADBL is highest than RBB and NBL. Then after NPL of RBB is highest and NPL of NBL is lowest. All are government banks and NPL in those banks are higher, shows the reckless lending and untidy long process in recovery management. Similarly, the long process in decision regarding recovery management leads them to higher NPL in comparison to other private commercial banks.

According NPL, the performance of NBL is good than RBB and ADBL due to lowest NPL in comparison to the other sample commercial banks.

4.4 Analysis of Credit Deposit Ratio (C/D) Ratio of Sample Commercial Banks

It is the ratio of how much a bank lends out of the deposits it has mobilized. The regulator does not stipulate a minimum or maximum level for the ratio. But, a very low

ratio indicates banks are not making full use of their resources. And if the ratio is above a certain level, it indicates a pressure on resources.

4.4.1 Analysis of Credit Deposit Ratio of RBB

It indicates how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending and vice-versa.

Table N0.4.13
Analysis of C/D Ratio of RBB

Year	Credit (crores)	Deposit (crores)	C/D Ratio (times)
2011/12	4045	8778	46.08
2012/13	4905	9109	53.84
2013/14	6085	10727	56.73
2014/15	7207	12422	61.05
2015/16	8178	14621	58.46
2016/17	10643	15358	69.30
2017/18	12087	16933	71.38
2018/19	14812	19199	77.15
2019/20	15652	23298	67.16
2020/21	19597	26620	73.62
Mean	10321.10	15706.50	63.48
S.D	5151.16	5952.14	9.84
Minimum	4045.00	8778.00	46.08
Maximum	19597.00	26620.00	77.15

Source: Annual Report of RBB

Table no. shows the credit to deposit ratio of RBB from F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. The C/D ratio is 46.08 times at 2011/12 and 77.15 times at 2018/19. The average C/D ratio is 63.48. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. C/D ratio of RBB is still below than the standard. It means that it still has idle fund to invest in the market which shows good financial performance of the bank in analysis period.

4.4.2 Analysis of Credit Deposit Ratio of ADBL.

C/D ratio gives the first indication of the health of a bank. A very high ratio is considered alarming because, in addition to indicating pressure on resources, it may

also hint at capital adequacy issues, forcing banks to raise more capital. Moreover, the balance sheet would also be unhealthy with asset-liability mismatches.

Table N0.4.14

Analysis of C/D Ratio of ADBL			
Year	Credit (crores)	Deposit (crores)	C/D Ratio (times)
2011/12	4498.84	4326.41	104.06
2012/13	5491.85	5447.77	100.81
2013/14	6247.29	6589.84	94.80
2014/15	7223.90	7703.5	93.77
2015/16	8341.80	8738.7	95.46
2016/17	9272.50	9981.60	92.90
2017/18	10016.60	10473.1	95.64
2018/19	11175.00	11936.3	93.62
2019/20	12337.70	14373.20	85.84
2020/21	15147.10	16299.00	92.93
Mean	8975.26	9586.94	94.98
S.D	3308.11	3836.61	4.86
Minimum	4498.84	4326.41	85.84
Maximum	15147.10	16299.00	104.06

Source: Annual Report of ADBL

Table no. 4.14 shows the credit to deposit ratio of ADBL from F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. The C/D ratio is 104.06 times at 2011/12 and 92.93 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio is 94.98. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. C/D ratio of ADBL is higher than the standard.

A very high ratio is considered alarming because, in addition to indicating pressure on resources, it may also hint at capital adequacy issues, forcing banks to raise more capital. Moreover, the balance sheet would also be unhealthy with asset-liability mismatches. But such a situation is considered extreme as there are not many known instances of banks over stretching themselves.

4.4.3 Analysis of Credit Deposit Ratio of NBL.

C/D ratio gives the first indication of the health of a bank. A very high ratio is considered alarming because, in addition to indicating pressure on resources, it may

also hint at capital adequacy issues, forcing banks to raise more capital. Moreover, the balance sheet would also be unhealthy with asset-liability mismatches.

Table N0.4.15

Analysis of C/D Ratio of NBL			
Year	Credit (crores)	Deposit (crores)	C/D Ratio (times)
2011/12	2969.90	5605.20	52.98
2012/13	3785.20	6298.40	60.10
2013/14	4121.80	6933.80	59.45
2014/15	5338.80	7799.90	68.45
2015/16	6352.40	8941.00	71.05
2016/17	7318.60	9394.40	79.17
2017/18	7829.60	9983.10	75.68
2018/19	9572.50	11827.50	78.14
2019/20	10682.50	14298.90	72.25
2020/21	14195.90	16362.30	82.76
Mean	7216.72	10127.34	70.00
S.D	3501.10	3485.65	9.74
Minimum	2969.90	5605.20	52.98
Maximum	14195.90	16362.30	82.76

Source: Annual Report of NBL

Table no. 4.15 shows the credit to deposit ratio of NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. The C/D ratio is 52.98 times at 2011/12 and 82.76 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio is 70. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. C/D ratio of NBL is almost at the standard.

A very high ratio is considered alarming because, in addition to indicating pressure on resources, it may also hint at capital adequacy issues, forcing banks to raise more capital. The regulator does not stipulate a minimum or maximum level for the ratio. But, a very low ratio indicates banks are not making full use of their resources. And if the ratio is above a certain level, it indicates a pressure on resources.

4.4.4 Analysis of Credit Deposit Ratio of Sample Commercial Banks

Credit-Deposit ratio shall reveal Banks position as regards to lending's against deposits, now what should be the appropriate percentage depends upon Banks maturity pattern of

deposits, repayment position on advances, etc. Banks have to be very careful lend after considering maturity pattern of deposits & out of order position of loan accounts and its maturity period.

Table N0.4.16

Analysis of C/D Ratio of Sample Commercial Banks (times)			
Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	46.08	104.06	52.98
2012/13	53.84	100.81	60.10
2013/14	56.73	94.80	59.45
2014/15	61.05	93.77	68.45
2015/16	58.46	95.46	71.05
2016/17	69.30	92.90	79.17
2017/18	71.38	95.64	75.68
2018/19	77.15	93.62	78.14
2019/20	67.16	85.84	72.25
2020/21	73.62	92.93	82.76
Mean	63.48	94.98	70.00
S.D	9.84	4.86	9.74
Minimum	46.08	85.84	52.98
Maximum	77.15	104.06	82.76

Source: Annual Report of Sample Commercial Banks

Figure 4.4 Analysis of C/D Ratio of Sample Commercial Banks (times)

Table no. and figure no. 4.4 shows the credit to deposit ratio of RBB, ADBL and NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity.

A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. The average C/D ratio of RBB is 63.48 times, ADBL has 94.98 times whereas NBL 70 times. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio of RBB is 77.15 times, ADBL has 104.06 times whereas NBL has 82.76 times during analysis period.

RBB and NBL is in comfort zone of C/D ratio while ADBL has to downsize of C/D ratio to meet the standard. To downsize either deposit volume is to be increased or loan amount is to be decreased.

According to the above figure, C/D ratio of ADBL is more than 100% whereas C/D ratio of RBB and NBL is lower than ABBL. The minimum standard of C/D ratio is 90 % now. The minimum C/D ratio explained the comfort zone of bank to lend in the credit in the market. According to the standard NBL has also maintained the C/D ratio under the standard but the performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL.

4.5 Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio of Sample Commercial Banks

The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is a measure of how much capital a bank has available, reported as a percentage of a bank's risk-weighted credit exposures. The capital used to calculate the capital adequacy ratio is divided into two tiers. Capital is

broken down as Tier-1, core capital, such as equity and disclosed reserves, and Tier-2, supplemental capital held as part of a bank's required reserves.

4.5.1 Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of RBB

The capital adequacy ratio is calculated by dividing a bank's capital by its risk-weighted assets.

Table N0.4.17
Analysis of CAR of RBB (times)

Year	Core Capital	Supplementary Capital	Capital Adequacy Ratio
2011/12	(9.77)	-	(9.77)
2012/13	1.51	1.43	2.94
2013/14	4.46	0.16	4.62
2014/15	10.16	-	10.16
2015/16	9.31	1.14	10.46
2016/17	9.15	1.24	10.39
2017/18	9.98	1.48	11.46
2018/19	12.31	1.08	13.39
2019/20	11.42	1.22	12.64
2020/21	11.09	2.37	13.46
Mean	6.96	1.01	7.98
Minimum	-9.77	0.00	-9.77
Maximum	12.31	2.37	13.46

Source: Annual Report of RBB

Table no. 4.17 shows the capital adequacy report of RBB from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. RBB has negative CAR at F/Y 2011/12 and 13.46 at F/Y 2020/21. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times

The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times, but it has fail to meet the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2020/21 and F/Y 2016/17. Therefore, the lower a bank's CAR, the more likely it is not to be able to withstand a financial downturn or other unforeseen losses. A bank with a high capital adequacy ratio is considered to be above the minimum requirements needed to suggest solvency.

4.5.2 Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of ADBL

The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is defined as a measurement of a bank's available capital expressed as a percentage of a bank's risk-weighted credit exposures. Minimum capital adequacy ratios are critical in ensuring that banks have enough cushion to

absorb a reasonable amount of losses before they become insolvent and consequently lose depositors' funds. The purpose is to establish that banks have enough capital on reserve to handle a certain amount of losses, before being at risk for becoming insolvent.

Table N0.4.18
Analysis of CAR of ADBL (times)

Year	Core Capital	Supplementary Capital	Capital Adequacy Ratio
2011/12	15.72	3.28	19.00
2012/13	13.61	2.72	16.34
2013/14	12.49	2.44	14.93
2014/15	11.96	2.94	13.90
2015/16	15.17	1.99	17.16
2016/17	18.61	1.80	20.41
2017/18	19.28	1.05	20.33
2018/19	19.27	1.10	20.37
2019/20	16.47	2.82	19.29
2020/21	14.42	2.53	16.94
Mean	15.70	2.27	17.87
Minimum	11.96	1.05	13.90
Maximum	19.28	3.28	20.41

Source: Annual Report of ADBL

Table no. 4.18 shows the capital adequacy report of ADBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. ADBL has CAR of 19.00 at F/Y 2011/12 and 16.94 at F/Y 2020/21. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. It has meet the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2020/21. Therefore, the higher a bank's CAR, the more likely it is to be able to withstand a financial downturn or other unforeseen losses. Minimum capital adequacy ratios are critical in ensuring that banks have enough cushion to absorb a reasonable amount of losses before they become insolvent and consequently lose depositors' funds.

4.5.3 Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of NBL

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is the ratio of a bank's capital in relation to its risk weighted assets and current liabilities. It is decided by central banks and bank regulators to prevent commercial banks from taking excess leverage and becoming insolvent in the

process. A bank with a high capital adequacy ratio is considered to be above the minimum requirements needed to suggest solvency.

Table No.4.19

Analysis of CAR of NBL (times)			
Year	Core Capital	Supplementary Capital	Capital Adequacy Ratio
2011/12	(5.82)	-	(5.82)
2012/13	(0.59)	-	(0.59)
2013/14	3.92	0.63	4.55
2014/15	6.32	1.17	7.49
2015/16	9.01	1.19	10.20
2016/17	13.37	1.10	14.47
2017/18	10.29	0.98	11.27
2018/19	15.87	0.93	16.80
2019/20	16.00	1.01	17.01
2020/21	13.54	3.26	16.80
Mean	8.19	1.03	9.22
Minimum	-5.82	0.00	-5.82
Maximum	16.00	3.26	17.01

Source: Annual Report of NBL

Table no. 4.19 shows the capital adequacy report of NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. NBL has negative CAR of 5.82 times and 0.59 times at F/Y 2011/12 and F/Y 2012/13. It has CAR of 16.80 times at F/Y 2020/21. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times the minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. It has fail to meet the requirement till F/Y2014/15 and meet the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2020/21. Therefore, the higher a bank's CAR, the more likely it is to be able to withstand a financial downturn or other unforeseen losses. The Capital Adequacy Ratio set standards for banks by looking at a bank's ability to pay liabilities, and respond to credit risks and operational risks.

A bank that has a good CAR has enough capital to absorb potential losses. Thus, it has less risk of becoming insolvent and losing depositors' money.

4.5.4 Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of Sample Commercial Banks

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is also known as Capital to Risk (Weighted) Assets Ratio (CRAR), is the ratio of a bank's capital to its risk. It is a measure of a bank's capital. It is expressed as a percentage of a bank's risk-weighted credit exposures.

The Bank of International Settlements separates capital into Tier 1 and Tier 2 based on the function and quality of the capital. Tier 1 capital is the primary way to measure a bank's financial health. It includes shareholder's equity and retained earnings, which are disclosed on financial statements.

Table N0.4.20

Analysis of CAR of Sample Commercial Banks (times)			
Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	(9.77)	19.00	(5.82)
2012/13	2.94	16.34	(0.59)
2013/14	4.62	14.93	4.55
2014/15	10.16	13.90	7.49
2015/16	10.46	17.16	10.20
2016/17	10.39	20.41	14.47
2017/18	11.46	20.33	11.27
2018/19	13.39	20.37	16.80
2019/20	12.64	19.29	17.01
2020/21	13.46	16.94	16.80
Mean	7.98	17.87	9.22
Minimum	-9.77	13.90	-5.82
Maximum	13.46	20.41	17.01

Source: Annual Report of Sample Commercial Banks

Figure 4.5 Analysis of capital adequacy ratio of Sample Commercial Banks

Table no. 4.20 and figure no. 4.5 shows the Capital adequacy ratio of RBB, ADBL and NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. National regulators track a bank's CAR to ensure that it can absorb a reasonable amount of loss and complies with statutory Capital requirements.

The average CAR ratio of RBB is 7.98 times, ADBL has 17.87 times whereas NBL 9.22 times. The maximum CAR ratio of RBB is 13.46 times, ADBL has 20.41 times whereas NBL has 17.01 times during analysis period.

ADBL is in comfort zone of CAR ratio while NBL and RBB has to increase the CAR ratio to protect depositors and promote stability and efficiency of financial systems around the world.

The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. The Capital adequacy ratio of ADBL is highest and above the minimum standard as set by the central bank whereas CAR of NBL and RBB is lower than ADBL. CAR of NBL and RBB is even negative in starting of F/Y. According to CAR the financial performance of ADBL is far better than NBL and RBB.

4.6 Ratio Analysis

Ratio analysis is the process of determining the significant operation and financial characteristics of a firm from accounting data and financial statement. The goal of such analysis is to determine the efficiency and performance of the firm's management as reflected in the financial records and reports.

4.6.1 Return on Total Assets (ROA)

ROA, refers to a financial ratio that indicates how profitable a company is in relation to its total assets is used to determine how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate a profit. It is commonly expressed as a percentage. A higher ROA means a company is more efficient and productive at managing its balance sheet to generate profits while a lower ROA indicates there is room for improvement.

Table 4.21
Return on Total Assets (ROA) Ratio (times)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	1.23	2.90	0.30
2012/13	1.26	2.97	1.07
2013/14	1.47	1.76	0.92
2014/15	3.22	3.12	0.55
2015/16	1.42	2.32	2.79
2016/17	1.6	2.15	2.78
2017/18	1.42	2.71	2.41
2018/19	2.23	2.77	1.51
2019/20	1.64	1.86	1.22
2020/21	1.10	1.59	1.33

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Figure 4.6 Analysis of ROA of Sample Commercial Banks

Table no. 4.21 and figure no. 4.6 shows the ROA of three government banks, RBB, ADBL and NBL from the F/Y 2011/12 to 2020/21. ROA of RBB lies 1.10 times to 3.22 times. ROA of ADBL lies between 1.59 times 3.12 times. It is decreasing in the succeeding years. ROA of NBL lies between 0.30 times to 2.79 times.

ROA of NBL is quite lower than other two banks. It shows that NBL is earning lower amount in comparison to investment in total assets in comparison to two others banks. The total assets of NBL is still underutilized. The total assets must be optimum utilized to achieve the high amount of profit. Higher the ratio indicates the success of management in overall operation and in earning net profit with efficient utilization of total assets.

ROA of ADBL is almost higher than RBB and NBL. It means that ADBL is quite utilizing its assets to generate profit. According to ROA, ADBL has good performance in comparison to NBL and RBB. NBL and RBB is following to the ADBL in utilizing its assets to generate profit.

4.6.2 Earning per share (EPS)

Earnings per share, or EPS, is a ratio that compares a company's profits with the number of shares outstanding to evaluate profitability. EPS is calculated by taking a company's net income and subtracting dividends, and then dividing that number by the number of outstanding shares.

Table 4.22
Earnings per share (EPS) Ratio (in Rs.)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	307.49	45.09	46.36
2012/13	21.79	59.03	198.53
2013/14	21.38	35.19	18.08
2014/15	54.07	78.83	7.48
2015/16	27.42	52.79	44.59
2016/17	32.32	31.59	38.77
2017/18	30.26	36.91	39.98
2018/19	56.04	42.88	26.99
2019/20	48.61	31.45	20.68
2020/21	37.27	29.13	23.43

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Figure 4.7 Analysis of EPS of Sample Commercial Banks

Table no.4.22 and figure no. 4.7 shows the earning per share (EPS) of sample commercial banks from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. EPS of RBB, ADBL and NBL is Rs.307.49, Rs.45.09 and Rs.46.36 respectively in F/Y 2011/12. Similarly, EPS of RBB, ADBL and NBL is Rs.37.27, Rs.29.13 and Rs.23.43 respectively in F/Y 2020/21.

ADBL has lead in EPS till F/Y 2015/16. Then NBL has lead in EPS in F/Y 2016/17 and 2017/18. Similarly, RBB has made a lead in EPS from F/Y 2018/19 to F/Y 2020/21. It seems that there is completion in leading in EPS between RBB, ADBL and NBL during the analysis period.

EPS of RBB has fallen from the very peak point in the coming F/Y in comparison to F/Y 2011/12. EPS of all sample commercial banks are decreasing and not constant to the previous analysis period.

The financial performance of sample commercial banks is lower in comparison to their own previous performance in analysis period but the financial performance of all sample commercial banks are same in comparison the comparative financial performance of sample commercial banks.

4.6.3 Dividend per share (DPS)

Dividend per share (DPS) is the sum of declared dividends issued by a company for every ordinary share outstanding. The figure is calculated by dividing the total dividends paid out by a business, including interim dividends, over a period of time,

usually a year, by the number of outstanding ordinary shares issued. A company's DPS is often derived using the dividend paid in the most recent quarter, which is also used to calculate the dividend yield.

Table 4.23
Dividend per share (DPS) Ratio (in Rs.)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	1.00	0	0
2012/13	0	31.58	0
2013/14	0	15.79	0
2014/15	0	15.79	0
2015/16	0	21.05	0
2016/17	0	21.05	0
2017/18	0	21.05	0
2018/19	0	30.00	25.00
2019/20	12.00	15.79	16.00
2020/21	4.50	21.05	17.00

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Figure 4.8 Analysis of Dividend per share (DPS) Ratio (in Rs.)

Table no. 4.23 and figure no. 4.8 shows the dividend per share (DPS) of sample commercial banks from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. DPS of RBB, ADBL and

NBL is Rs.1.00, Rs.0 and Rs.0 respectively in F/Y 2011/12. Similarly, DPS of RBB, ADBL and NBL is Rs.4.50, Rs.21.05 and Rs.17.00 respectively in F/Y 2020/21.

ADBL has lead in EPS till F/Y 2018/19. Then NBL has lead in EPS in F/Y 2019/20. Similarly, RBB has made a lead in EPS in F/Y 2020/21. It seems that ADBL has lead in EPS during the analysis period.

DPS of all sample commercial banks are decreasing and not constant to the previous analysis period. ADBL is constantly paying dividend to its valued customer from the starting analysis period. The financial performance of ADBL is far better than NBL and RBB on the basis of DPS in comparison the comparative financial performance of sample commercial banks.

4.6.4 Market price share (MPS)

Market value per share is calculated as the total market value of the business, divided by the total number of shares outstanding. This reveals the value that the market currently assigns to each share of a company's stock.

These ratios are not closely watched by the managers of a business, since these individuals are more concerned with operational issues. The main exception is the investor relations officer, who must be able to see the company's performance from the perspective of investors, and so is much more likely to track these measurements closely. Market value ratios are not applied to the shares of privately-held entities, since there is no accurate way to assign a market value to their shares.

Table 4.24
Market per share (MPS) Ratio (in Rs.)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	0	156	0
2012/13	0	212	171
2013/14	0	756	459
2014/15	0	432	305
2015/16	0	768	470
2016/17	0	435	364
2017/18	0	314	281
2018/19	0	409	336
2019/20	0	385	249
2020/21	0	479	443

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Figure No. 4.9 Analysis of Market per share (MPS) Ratio (in Rs.)

Table no 4.24 and figure no. 4.9 shows the market per share (MPS) of sample commercial banks from the F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. MPS of RBB, and NBL is Rs.0 respectively in F/Y 2011/12. MPS of ADBL is Rs.156 in F/Y 2011/12. Similarly, MPS of RBB, ADBL and NBL is Rs.0, Rs.479 and Rs.443 respectively in F/Y 2020/21. ADBL has lead in MPS in all F/Y in MPS. NBL is following to ADBL. Since RBB is not listed in Nepal stock exchange, it is not traded in the market. So it has no any market price per share.

MPS of all sample commercial banks are decreasing and not constant to the previous analysis period. The financial performance of ADBL is far better than NBL and RBB on the basis of MPS in comparison the comparative financial performance of sample commercial banks

4.6.5 Debt Assets Ratio

It measures proportion of the creditor's funds used by the institution to acquire the assets. The increased proportion of debt indicated the risk or burden to the institution. The debt is considering riskier and also cheap source of financing. It is risky in the sense that the debt financing needs regular payment of interest in any condition of economy. The debt asset ratios of sample banks are as below:

Table 4.25
Debt to Total Assets Ratio (Rs. In crores)

Year	RBB			ADBL			NBL		
	Debt	Total Assets	Ratio (%)	Debt	Total Assets	Ratio (%)	Debt	Total Assets	Ratio (%)
2011/12	8841	9391	94.14%	5404	6352	85.08%	5543	6392	86.72%
2012/13	9294	10152	91.55%	6746	7710	87.50%	7321	7465	98.07%
2013/14	11397	12256	92.99%	7665	8651	88.60%	7152	7798	91.72%
2014/15	13098	13956	93.85%	9055	10093	89.72%	8175	8821	92.68%
2015/16	15784	16643	94.84%	10023	11179	89.66%	9702	10348	93.76%
2016/17	16945	17354	97.64%	11293	12687	89.01%	10402	11206	92.83%
2017/18	17857	19763	90.36%	10889	13486	80.74%	11389	13681	83.25%
2018/19	20482	22641	90.46%	12311	15146	81.28%	14223	17152	82.92%
2019/20	24374	26677	91.37%	15085	17932	84.12%	16113	19116	84.29%
2020/21	28131	30999	90.75%	19094	22244	85.84%	18943	22265	85.08%

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Debt assets ratios of all the banks are seen to be very high. RBB has financed 90.75% to 97.64% of its assets by outsider's fund. ADBL has also financed 80.74% to 89.72% of its assets from the debt. Similarly, NBL has financed 83.25% to 98.07 % of its assets by outsider's fund. Above calculated ratios shows larger portion of the bank's asset has been financed through outsider's fund. This ratio shows that bank is following high profit high risk strategy.

4.6.6 Debt Equity Ratio

The Debt Equity ratio implies the debt equity proportion used by the institution High Debt Equity ratio indicates more use of money from creditors side and vice versa. High Debt Equity ratio is considered good if the institutions have higher return than the cost paid on debt.

Table 4.26
Debt to Equity Ratio (Rs. In Crores)

Year	RBB			ADBL			NBL		
	Debt	Equity	Ratio (Times)	Debt	Equity	Ratio (Times)	Debt	Equity	Ratio (Times)
2011/12	8841	550	16.07	5404	948	5.70	5543	647	8.57
2012/13	9294	859	10.82	6746	964	7.00	7321	647	11.32
2013/14	11397	859	13.27	7665	986	7.77	7152	647	11.05
2014/15	13098	668	19.61	9055	1038	8.72	8175	647	12.64
2015/16	16643	861	19.33	10023	1156	8.67	9702	647	15.00
2016/17	17354	1048	16.56	11293	1394	8.10	10402	804	12.94
2017/18	17857	1907	9.36	10889	2587	4.21	11389	2292	4.97
2018/19	20482	2159	9.49	12311	2835	4.34	14223	2928	4.86
2019/20	24374	2303	10.58	15085	2847	5.30	16113	3003	5.37
2020/21	28131	2867	16.07	19094	3151	5.70	18943	3322	8.57

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Total Debt includes long term and short term interest bearing obligation which are loans and advances taken from other financial institution and deposits carrying interest i.e. saving deposit, fixed deposit and call deposit. Equity is combination of paid of capital and reserve and surplus. Debt Equity Ratio shows the mix of debt and equity in capital structure.

Most of the investment and assets of the banks are financed by the debt. The debt of RBB is 16.07 times higher than equity in FY 2011/12. The Debt Equity ratio of RBB is in increasing trend. It becomes 19.61times in fiscal year 2014/15. Debt Equity ratio of ADBL is 4.21 to 8.67 times.

But NBL has the ratio of 8.57 times to 15 times respectively. It clearly shows that It seems that ADBL has used less amount of debt in comparison to RBB and NBL.

4.6.7 Equity to Total Assets

The Equity-To-Asset ratio measures the amount of equity the business or firm has when compared to the total assets owned by the business or farm. To determine the Equity-To-Asset ratio, the Net Worth is divided by the Total Assets. This ratio is measured as a percentage. This ratio shows the proportion of equity to the total assets. The higher the equity to asset ratio, the less debt the company has and the less risky it is. A low equity to asset ratio means the company has more debt and is riskier. The equity to asset ratio is

important because it shows how much equity a company has compared to its total assets. A high equity to asset ratio means the company is less risky, and vice-versa. Proportion of equity capital of RBB, ADBL and NBL can be shown as below.

Table 4.27
Equity to Total Assets Ratio (Rs. In Crores)

Year	RBB			ADBL			NBL		
	Equity	Total Assets	Ratio (%)	Equity	Total Assets	Ratio (%)	Equity	Total Assets	Ratio (%)
2011/12	550	9391	5.86%	948	6352	14.92%	647	6392	10.12%
2012/13	859	10152	8.46%	964	7710	12.50%	647	7465	8.67%
2013/14	859	12256	7.01%	986	8651	11.40%	647	7798	8.30%
2014/15	668	13956	4.79%	1038	10093	10.28%	647	8821	7.33%
2015/16	861	16643	5.17%	1156	11179	10.34%	647	10348	6.25%
2016/17	1048	17354	6.04%	1394	12687	10.99%	804	11206	7.17%
2017/18	1907	19763	9.65%	2587	13486	19.18%	2292	13681	16.75%
2018/19	2159	22641	9.54%	2835	15146	18.72%	2928	17152	17.07%
2019/20	2303	26677	8.63%	2847	17932	15.88%	3003	19116	15.71%
2020/21	2867	30999	5.86%	3151	22244	14.92%	3322	22265	10.12%

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

Table no. 4.27 shows the ratio of equity capital and total assets of RBB, ADBL and NBL from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2020/21. It shows that the equity ratio of RBB is comparatively lower than ADBL and NBL. The equity portion of RBB lies between 4.79% to 9.65%. The equity portion of ADBL lies between 10.28% to 19.18%. Similarly, the equity portion of NBL lies between 6.25% to 17.07%. Equity portion of RBB is lower due to fully ownership of bank is governed by Nepal government. As assets of the bank are also increasing, the ratio of equity to total assets is decreasing. Equity to total assets of NBL is more fluctuating than others.

4.6.8 Loan Advances to Total Deposit Ratio

This ratio measures the extent to which the banks are successful to mobilize the total deposits on loans and advances for the purpose of income generation. The following

table exhibits the ratio of loans and advances to total deposits of the banks throughout the study period.

Table 4.28

Year	Loan & Advances to Total Deposit Ratio (Rs. In Crores)								
	RBB			ADBL			NBL		
	Loans & Advances	Total Deposit	Ratio (%)	Loans & Advances	Total Deposit	Ratio (%)	Loans & Advances	Total Deposit	Ratio (%)
2011/12	4045	8778	46.08	4498.84	4326.41	104.06	2969.90	5605.20	52.98
2012/13	4905	9109	53.84	5491.85	5447.77	100.81	3785.20	6298.40	60.10
2013/14	6085	10727	56.73	6247.29	6589.84	94.80	4121.80	6933.80	59.45
2014/15	7207	12422	61.05	7223.90	7703.5	93.77	5338.80	7799.90	68.45
2015/16	8178	14621	58.46	8341.80	8738.7	95.46	6352.40	8941.00	71.05
2016/17	10643	15358	69.30	9272.50	9981.60	92.90	7318.60	9394.40	79.17
2017/18	12087	16933	71.38	10016.60	10473.1	95.64	7829.60	9983.10	75.68
2018/19	14812	19199	77.15	11175.00	11936.3	93.62	9572.50	11827.50	78.14
2019/20	15652	23298	67.16	12337.70	14373.20	85.84	10682.50	14298.90	72.25
2020/21	19597	26620	73.62	15147.10	16299.00	92.93	14195.90	16362.30	82.76

(Source: Annual Report of the Concerned Banks)

The ratio indicates the proportion of total deposit invested in loans and advances. Out of the total deposit of RBB has invested 46.08% to 73.62% of total deposit to loan and advances. ADBL has invested 85.84% to 104.06% of total deposit in loan and advances. Similarly, NBL has invested 52.98% to 82.76% of total deposit to loan and advances.

As per banking practice, banks maintain the ratio around 65- 90%. Above table shows banks are successful in utilizing its deposits on loans and advances. But the trend of utilization is fluctuating for both the banks. It seems that NBL and RBB is in comfort zone whereas ADBL must have to downsize the loan amount or to increase the deposit amount to meet the requirement.

4.7 Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis testing is an act in statistics whereby an analyst tests an assumption regarding a population parameter. The methodology employed by the analyst depends on the nature of the data used and the reason for the analysis.

Hypothesis testing is used to assess the plausibility of a hypothesis by using sample data. Such data may come from a larger population, or from a data-generating process.

The word "population" will be used for both of these cases in the following descriptions.

Let r be the observed sample correlation coefficient a sample of n pairs of observations from bi-variate normal population. In order to test whether the sample correlation coefficient is significant of any correlation between the variables in the population, t -test for significance of an observed sample correlation coefficient is applied. The steps for testing of significance of an observed sample correlation coefficient are as follows.

Step-1 Null Hypothesis (H_0): $\rho = 0$: that is population correlation coefficient is zero. In other words, the variables are not significantly (insignificant) correlated in the population i.e. r is not significant (insignificant) of correlation in the population. It indicates that the two population variables are uncorrelated.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): $\rho \neq 0$: that is population correlation coefficient is not zero. In other words, the variables are significantly correlated in the population i.e. r is significant of correlation in the population. It indicates that two population variables are correlated.

Step-2 Test statistic, under H_0 , the test statistics is;

$$t = \frac{r}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \times \sqrt{n-2}$$

Where t_{n-2} i.e. follows, t -distribution with $(n-2)$ d.f

n = being the sample.

r = simple correlation coefficient

Step-3 Obtained the tabulated value of t for $(n-2)$ d.f. at α level of significance according as whether the alternative hypothesis is one tailed or two tailed test.

Step-4 Decision: Make a decision by comparing the calculated value of t with tabulated value of t , it is not significant and it is accepted otherwise, it is rejected.

4.7.1 Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of (RBB)

The table 4.29 summarizes correlation coefficient(r), coefficient of determination(r^2), covariance and hypothesis testing analysis and the tabulated value(t_{tab}) and calculated value(t_{cal}) of " t " of Rastriya Banijya Bank (RBB) over last 10 (ten years) and shows the relationship (correlation) of loan and advances to total deposit along with the significance of such relationship.

Table No. 4.29
Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of (RBB)

Variables	Correlation (r)	Coefficient of determination(r^2)	Covariance	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Remarks
Loan to Deposit	0.99	0.97	30843872.61	16.25	1.5125	Significant

According to Table no. 4.29, the correlation analysis shows that loan and advances is positively correlated with deposit which mean that any increase in deposit leads to increase in the loan and advances and decrease in deposit will lead to decrease in loan and advances. 99% change in loan is explained by deposit.

The correlation between loan and advances with deposit is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.97, which indicates that nearly 97% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 3% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.

The simple correlation of coefficients of loan and advances with deposit is significant at 95% confidence limit. Hence we conclude the sample has not come from the normal population with zero correlation (two tailed test). It means there is correlation between two population variables i.e. loan and advances with deposit.

4.7.2 Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of (ADBL)

The table 4.30 summarizes correlation coefficient(r), coefficient of determination(r^2), covariance and hypothesis testing analysis and the tabulated value(t_{tab}) and calculated value(t_{cal}) of "t" of Agriculture Development Bank Limited (ADBL) over last 10 (ten years) and shows the relationship (correlation) of loan and advances to total deposit along with the significance of such relationship.

Table No. 4.30
Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of ADBL

Variables	Correlation (r)	Coefficient of determination(r^2)	Covariance	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Remarks
Loan to Deposit	0.99	0.99	12693456.88	28.14	1.5125	Significant

According to Table no. 4.30, the correlation analysis shows that loan and advances is positively correlated with deposit which mean that any increase in deposit leads to increase in the loan and advances and decrease in deposit will lead to decrease in loan and advances. 99% change in loan is explained by deposit.

The correlation between loan and advances with deposit is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.99, which indicates that nearly 99% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 1% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.

The simple correlation of coefficients of loan and advances with deposit is significant at 95% confidence limit. Hence we conclude the sample has not come from the normal population with zero correlation (two tailed test). It means there is correlation between two population variables i.e. loan and advances with deposit.

4.7.3 Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of (NBL)

The table 4.31 summarizes correlation coefficient(r), coefficient of determination(r^2), covariance, hypothesis testing analysis and the tabulated value(t_{tab}) and calculated value(t_{cal}) of "t" of Nepal Bank Limited (NBL) over last 10 (ten years) and shows the relationship (correlation) of loan and advances to total deposit along with the significance of such relationship.

Table No. 4.31
Correlation, Covariance and Hypothesis testing analysis of NBL

Variables	Correlation (r)	Coefficient of determination(r^2)	Covariance	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Remarks
Loan to Deposit	0.99	0.98	12160066.00	19.90	1.5125	Significant

According to Table no. 4.31, the correlation analysis shows that loan and advances is positively correlated with deposit which mean that any increase in deposit leads to increase in the loan and advances and decrease in deposit will lead to decrease in loan and advances. 99% change in loan is explained by deposit.

The correlation between loan and advances with deposit is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.98, which indicates that nearly 98% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 2% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.

The simple correlation of coefficients of loan and advances with deposit is significant at 95% confidence limit. Hence we conclude the sample has not come from the normal population with zero correlation (two tailed test). It means there is correlation between two population variables i.e. loan and advances with deposit.

4.8 Trend Analysis of deposit, loan and ROA of Sample Commercial Banks

Trend analysis is a technique used in technical analysis that attempts to predict future stock price movements based on recently observed trend data. Trend analysis uses historical data, such as price movements and trade volume, to forecast the long-term direction of market sentiment. Trend analysis tries to predict a trend, such as a bull market run, and then ride that trend until data suggests a trend reversal, such as a bull-to-bear market.

Analyzing various financial data of three selected banks (If we deem this three bank as a sample representing the whole financial institution) it can be predicted the future economic event or condition through trend analysis of various indicators mainly deposit

reserve, loans & advances, investments, net income, return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) of financial institutes.

4.8.1 Trend Analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks

The Banking sector acts as the life blood of modern trade and economic development. Commercial banks influence, facilitate and integrate the economic activities like resources mobilization, poverty elimination, production, and distribution of public finance. The financial performance of commercial banks has great implications in the financial sector.

Table No.4.32

Trend analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks (crores)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	8778	4326.41	5605.20
2012/13	9109	5447.76	6298.40
2013/14	10727	6589.84	6933.80
2014/15	12422	7703.50	7799.99
2015/16	14621	8738.70	8941.00
2016/17	15358	9981.60	9394.40
2017/18	16933	10473.10	9983.10
2018/19	19199	11936.30	11827.5
2019/20	23298	14373.20	14298.90
2020/21	26620	16299.00	16362.30
2021/22	27257.54	16470.80	15887.41
2022/23	28175.91	17722.41	17004.31
2023/24	30094.28	18974.02	18121.21
2024/25	32012.65	20225.63	19238.11
2025/26	33931.02	21477.24	20355.01

Source: Annexure

Table no. 4.32 reveals the analysis of deposit of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of deposit from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The deposit of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The deposit of RBB is highest at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 26620 crores and ADBL has lowest deposit i.e.16299.00. The trend analysis up to F/Y 2025/26 shows that RBB will have highest

deposit i.e. 33931.02 crores and NBL will have lowest deposit i.e. 20355.01 crores in F/Y 2025/26.

The trend analysis the increasing trend of deposit of RBB is highest than other sample commercial banks and NBL has lowest increasing trend of deposit. The deposit of RBB will be Rs.33931.02 crores in F/Y 2025/26. Similarly, the deposit of ADBL will be Rs.21477.24 crores and the deposit of NBL will be Rs.20355.01 in F/Y 2025/26.

According to trend analysis, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can invest the collected deposit in form of loan in the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.

The trend analysis of deposit of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26 can be presented as below figure.

Figure No.4.10 Trend analysis of deposit of Sample Commercial Banks (crores)

Figure no. 4.10 reveals the analysis of deposit of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of deposit from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The deposit of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The deposit of RBB is highest at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 26620 crores and ADBL has lowest deposit i.e.16299.00. The trend analysis up to F/Y 2025/26 shows that RBB will have highest deposit i.e. 33931.02 crores and NBL will have lowest deposit i.e. 20355.01 crores in F/Y 2025/26.

The trend analysis the increasing trend of deposit of RBB is highest than other sample commercial banks and NBL has lowest increasing trend of deposit. The deposit of RBB will be Rs.33931.02 crores in F/Y 2025/26. Similarly, the deposit of ADBL will be Rs.21477.24 crores and the deposit of NBL will be Rs.20355.01 in F/Y 2025/26.

According to trend analysis, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can invest the collected deposit in form of loan in the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.

4.8.2 Trend Analysis of Loan of Sample Commercial Banks

Loan Trend Reports are considered operational analysis tools and are used by executives and loan managers to monitor trends and anomalies in branch-level and consolidated loan metrics. Banks use Loan Trend Reports to give managers a clear picture of trends and anomalies in the loan portfolio of each branch.

Table No.4.33
Trend of Loan and Advances of Sample Commercial Banks

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	3045	4498.84	2969.90
2012/13	4905	5491.85	3785.20
2013/14	6085	6247.29	4121.80
2014/15	7584	7223.85	5338.80
2015/16	8547	8341.83	6352.40
2016/17	10643	9770.31	7318.60
2017/18	12087	10398.72	7829.60
2018/19	14812	11175.02	9572.50
2019/20	15652	12337.71	10683.00
2020/21	19597	15147.07	14195.91
2021/22	19743.60	15041.48	13383.81
2022/23	21461.40	16128.43	14505.09
2023/24	23179.20	17215.38	15626.37
2024/25	24897.00	18302.33	16747.65
2025/26	26614.80	19389.28	17868.93

Source: Annexure

Table no. 4.33 reveals the analysis of loan of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of loan from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The loan of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The loan of RBB is highest

at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 19597 crores and NBL has lowest loan i.e.14195.91 The trend analysis the increasing trend of loan of RBB is highest than other sample commercial banks and NBL has lowest increasing trend of loan. The loan of RBB, ADBL and NBL will be Rs.26614.80 crores, Rs.19389.28 crores Rs.17868.93 respectively in F/Y 2025/26. According to trend analysis, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can generate high interest from loan from the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.

The trend analysis of loan of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26 can be presented as below figure.

Figure No.4.11 Trend analysis of Loan of Sample Commercial Banks (crores)

Figure no. 4.11 reveals the analysis of loan of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of loan from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The loan of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The loan of RBB is highest at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 19597 crores and NBL has lowest loan i.e.14195.91.

The trend analysis the increasing trend of loan of RBB is highest than other sample commercial banks and NBL has lowest increasing trend of loan. The loan of RBB, ADBL and NBL will be Rs.26614.80 crores, Rs.19389.28 crores Rs.17868.93 respectively in F/Y 2025/26. According to trend analysis, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can generate high interest from loan from the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.

4.8.3 Trend Analysis of ROA of Sample Commercial Banks

ROA compares the value of a business's assets with the profits it produces over a set period of time. Return on assets is a tool used by managers and financial analysts to determine how effectively a company is using its resources to make a profit.

Table 4.34
Trend Analysis of Return on Total Assets (ROA) Ratio (times)

Year	RBB	ADBL	NBL
2011/12	1.23	2.90	0.30
2012/13	1.26	2.97	1.07
2013/14	1.47	1.76	0.92
2014/15	3.22	3.12	0.55
2015/16	1.42	2.32	2.79
2016/17	1.6	2.15	2.78
2017/18	1.42	2.71	2.41
2018/19	2.23	2.77	1.51
2019/20	1.64	1.86	1.22
2020/21	1.10	1.59	1.33
2021/22	1.66	1.87	2.10
2022/23	1.66	1.77	2.21
2023/24	1.66	1.67	2.32
2024/25	1.66	1.57	2.43
2025/26	1.66	1.47	2.54

Source: Annexure

Table no. 4.34 reveals the ROA of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of ROA from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The ROA of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The ROA of ADBL is highest at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 1.59 times and RBB has lowest ROA i.e.1.10 times. The trend analysis shows that NBL will have highest ROA i.e. 2.54 times and ADBL will have lowest ROA i.e. 1.47 times in F/Y 2025/26. The trend analysis of ROA of NBL is highest than other sample commercial banks and ADBL has lowest increasing trend of ROA. ROA of RBB, ADBL and NBL will be 1.66 times 1.47 times and 2.54 times respectively in F/Y 2025/26. According to trend analysis, the financial performance of NBL is far

better than ADBL and RBB. It shows the optimum utilization of assets to generate profit and income which will lead NBL in competitive market.

The trend analysis of ROA of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26 can be presented as below figure.

Figure No.4.12 Trend Analysis of Return on Total Assets (ROA) Ratio (times)

Figure no. 4.12 reveals the ROA of sample commercial banks from F/Y 2011/12 to F/Y 2025/26 and trend analysis of ROA from F/Y 2021/22 to F/Y 2025/26. The ROA of sample commercial banks is in increasing trend. The ROA of ADBL is highest at F/Y 2020/21 i.e. 1.59 times and RBB has lowest ROA i.e.1.10 times. The trend analysis shows that NBL will have highest ROA i.e. 2.54 times and ADBL will have lowest ROA i.e. 1.47 times in F/Y 2025/26.

The trend analysis of ROA of NBL is highest than other sample commercial banks and ADBL has lowest increasing trend of ROA. ROA of RBB, ADBL and NBL will be 1.66 times 1.47 times and 2.54 times respectively in F/Y 2025/26. According to trend analysis, the financial performance of NBL is far better than ADBL and RBB. It shows the optimum utilization of assets to generate profit and income which will lead NBL in competitive market.

4.9 Major findings from Secondary Data Analysis

- The financial performance of RBB is greater than NBL and ADBL according to the loan disbursed. From the disbursed, RBB can collect highest amount of interest income, a major parameter of profit of the company.
- The deposit amount collected by the RBB is greater than ADBL and NBL. The deposit of NBL and ADBL is almost same in every F/Y.
- According to the deposit collected, the financial performance of RBB is good than ADBL and NBL. From the deposit collected, it can grant the loan to its valued customers.
- According NPL, the performance of NBL is good than RBB and ADBL due to lowest NPL in comparison to the other sample commercial banks.
- The C/D ratio of ADBL is more than 100% whereas C/D ratio of RBB and NBL is lower than ABBL. The minimum standard of C/D ratio is 90 % now. The minimum C/D ratio explained the comfort zone of bank to lend in the credit in the market.
- According to the standard NBL has also maintained the C/D ratio under the standard but the performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL.
- ADBL is in comfort zone of CAR ratio while NBL and RBB has to increase the CAR ratio to protect depositors and promote stability and efficiency of financial systems around the world.
- The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. The Capital adequacy ratio of ADBL is highest and above the minimum standard as set by the central bank whereas CAR of NBL and RBB is lower than ADBL. CAR of NBL and RBB is even negative in starting of F/Y. According to CAR the financial performance of ADBL is far better than NBL and RBB.
- The average deposit of RBB is highest than ADBL and NBL during analysis period. Similarly, NBL is following to RBB in collecting deposit rather than ADBL. The total deposit of RBB is highest in all F/Y and NBL has lowest deposit collected in the entire period. ADBL has lowest amount of loan in 2011/12 i.e.4326.41 crores but it has aggressively collected highest deposit in succeeding F/Y. It shows that RBB is has good performance in collecting deposit from its valued customers.

- RBB has highest and NBL has lowest NPL in average during analysis period. ADBL and NBL has lowest NPL in comparison to RBB. There is highest NPL in RBB and NBL in comparison to other ADBL. All are government banks and NPL in those banks are higher, shows the reckless lending and untidy long process in recovery management. Similarly, the long process in decision regarding recovery management leads them to higher NPL in comparison to other private commercial banks.
- The C/D ratio of RBB is 46.08 times at 2011/12 and 77.15 times at 2018/19. The average C/D ratio is 63.48. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. C/D ratio of RBB is still below than the standard. It means that it still has idle fund to invest in the market which shows good financial performance of the bank in analysis period.
- The C/D ratio of ADBL is 104.06 times at 2011/12 and 92.93 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio is 94.98. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. C/D ratio of ADBL is higher than the standard.
- The C/D ratio of NBL is 52.98 times at 2011/12 and 82.76 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio of NBL is 70 times. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. C/D ratio of NBL is almost at the standard.
- The average C/D ratio of RBB is 63.48 times, ADBL has 94.98 times whereas NBL 70 times. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio of RBB is 77.15 times, ADBL has 104.06 times whereas NBL has 82.76 times during analysis period. RBB and NBL is in comfort zone of C/D ratio while ADBL has to downsize of C/D ratio to meet the standard. To downsize either deposit volume is to be increased or loan amount is to be decreased.
- RBB has negative CAR at F/Y 2011/12 and 13.46 at F/Y 2020/21. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times, but it has fail to meet the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2013/14 and F/Y 2016/17. Therefore, the lower a bank's CAR, the more likely it is not to be able to withstand a financial downturn or other unforeseen losses.

- ADBL has CAR of 19.00 at F/Y 2011/12 and 16.94 at F/Y 2020/21. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. It has met the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2020/21. Therefore, the higher a bank's CAR, the more likely it is to be able to withstand a financial downturn or other unforeseen losses.
- The minimum standard of CAR of NBL from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. It has failed to meet the requirement till F/Y 2014/15 and met the minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2020/21. The Capital Adequacy Ratio sets standards for banks by looking at a bank's ability to pay liabilities, and respond to credit risks and operational risks.
- The average CAR ratio of RBB is 7.98 times, ADBL has 17.87 times whereas NBL 9.22 times. The maximum CAR ratio of RBB is 13.46 times, ADBL has 20.41 times whereas NBL has 17.01 times during analysis period. ADBL is in comfort zone of CAR ratio while NBL and RBB has to increase the CAR ratio to protect depositors and promote stability and efficiency of financial systems around the world.
- RBB has financed 90.75% to 97.64% of its assets by outsider's fund. ADBL has also financed 80.74% to 89.72% of its assets from the debt. Similarly, NBL has financed 83.25% to 98.07% of its assets by outsider's fund. Above calculated ratios show larger portion of the bank's asset has been financed through outsider's fund. This ratio shows that bank is following high profit high risk strategy.
- Most of the investment and assets of the banks are financed by the debt. The debt of RBB is 16.07 times higher than equity in FY 2011/12. The Debt Equity ratio of RBB is in increasing trend. It becomes 19.61 times in fiscal year 2014/15. Debt Equity ratio of ADBL is 4.21 to 8.67 times. But NBL has the ratio of 8.57 times to 15 times respectively. It clearly shows that it seems that ADBL has used less amount of debt in comparison to RBB and NBL.
- The equity portion of RBB lies between 4.79% to 9.65%. The equity portion of ADBL lies between 10.28% to 19.18%. Similarly, the equity portion of NBL lies between 6.25% to 17.07%. Equity portion of RBB is lower due to full ownership of bank is governed by Nepal government. As assets of the bank are also increasing, the ratio of equity to total assets is decreasing. Equity to total assets of NBL is more fluctuating than others.
- NBL is earning lower amount in comparison to investment in total assets in comparison to two other banks. The total assets of NBL are still underutilized. The

total assets must be optimum utilized to achieve the high amount of profit. Higher the ratio indicates the success of management in overall operation and in earning net profit with efficient utilization of total assets

- RBB has invested 46.08% to 73.62% of total deposit to loan and advances. ADBL has invested 85.84% to 104.06% of total deposit in loan and advances. Similarly, NBL has invested 52.98% to 82.76% of total deposit to loan and advances. As per banking practice, banks maintain the ratio around 65-90%. Above table shows banks are successful in utilizing its deposits on loans and advances. But the trend of utilization is fluctuating for both the banks. It seems that NBL and RBB is in comfort zone whereas ADBL must have to downsize the loan amount or to increase the deposit amount to meet the requirement.
- The correlation between loan and advances with deposit of RBB is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.97, which indicates that nearly 97% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 3% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.
- The correlation between loan and advances with deposit of ADBL is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.99, which indicates that nearly 99% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 1% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.
- The correlation between loan and advances with deposit of NBL is 0.99 which shows that loan and advances is significantly highly positively correlated with deposit. It indicates that when deposit increases loan also increases and vice-versa. The coefficient of determination is 0.98, which indicates that nearly 98% of the total change in loan and advances is due to the effect of deposit and rest 2% change in loan and advances is due to other factors. The correlations of individual factors with

loan and advances has very high degree of association with deposit. We cannot conclude that any of single factors play more vital role to fix the loan.

- According to trend analysis of deposit, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can invest the collected deposit in form of loan in the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.
- According to trend analysis of loan, the financial performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL. RBB can generate high interest from loan from the market and generate high profit which will lead RBB in competitive market.
- According to trend analysis of ROA, the financial performance of NBL is far better than ADBL and RBB. It shows the optimum utilization of assets to generate profit and income which will lead NBL in competitive market.

4.10 Discussion

The average deposit of RBB is highest than ADBL and NBL during analysis period. Similarly, NBL is following to RBB in collecting deposit rather than ADBL. It shows that RBB is has good performance in collecting deposit from its valued customers.

RBB has highest and NBL has lowest NPL in average during analysis period. ADBL and NBL has lowest NPL in comparison to RBB. There is highest NPL in RBB and NBL in comparison to other ADBL. C/D ratio of RBB is still below than the standard. It means that it still has idle fund to invest in the market which shows good financial performance of the bank in analysis period.

The financial performance of RBB is greater than NBL and ADBL according to the loan disbursed. From the disbursed, RBB can collect highest amount of interest income, a major parameter of profit of the company. The deposit amount collected by the RBB is greater than ADBL and NBL.

ADBL is in comfort zone of CAR ratio while NBL and RBB has to increase the CAR ratio to protect depositors and promote stability and efficiency of financial systems around the world. The Capital adequacy ratio of ADBL is highest and above the minimum standard as set by the central bank whereas CAR of NBL and RBB is lower than ADBL.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this chapter, three major aspects of the study are discussed. In the beginning all the findings have been summarized and some conclusions have been drawn up based on findings. Then, the gaps found and factors that caused those gaps are also presented. This chapter is very important in the following senses:

- a. It shows a glance of the study what is observed during research.
- b. It concludes the findings in an understandable form
- c. It provides some suggestion to the concerned authority as well as practitioner and academicians. The recommendation is presented in this chapter considering the major findings and gaps found there too.

5.1 Summary

Industrialization is an important factor for achieving the basic objective of a country's economic and social progress. Industrialization not only provides necessary products and services to the community but also creates employment opportunities. Industrial development thus has a multiplier effect on the economy. Banking industries have been regarded as one of the component of economy. It transfers the scattered funds collected from saving of the public into various productive sectors. Economic activities remains halt in absence of banking industries as it plays the role of catalyst for economic development of the country in the developing country where there prevail unorganized transactions. It helps to enhance economic activities of the country by providing capital funds for the smooth operation of business activities. It also helps to create employment opportunities, resource utilization, credit creation, income generation and economic development of the country.

Commercial banks in Nepal have come across a long way to reach at the present status they hold in the national economy. Since from the beginning of the establishment of Nepal Bank Limited (NBL) in 1937 A.D. to the present scenario with the emergence of new and growing banks have brought tremendous changes in terms of services, capacity development and the way they serve customers. Modern banking practices have been introduced by almost all the commercial banks in Nepal. Commercial banks that were initially involved merely in lending and deposit sector have now modified their traditional business concepts and introduced new services to Nepalese customer like, credit card, debit card, SMS banking, E-banking etc. Banking sectors has made

significant improvement after the Government of Nepal adopted liberal economic policy. One of the fast growing industries of Nepal is banking industry, after Nepal adopted liberal economic policy. But intense competition and lack of sufficient investment opportunities have created threat to banks. Therefore, future in the banking sector will be more competitive with quality and speedy service. Banks have to provide quality and speedy service and attain objectives along with maintaining social responsibility to sustain in market. Financial analysis is the process of identifying the financial strength and weakness of the firm by properly establishing relationship between the items of balance sheet and profit and loss account. Ratio analysis is used by financial analysts for making decisions. It will compare the bank's ratios to its past performance. Among 27 commercial banks of Nepal, three government banks, RBB, ADBL and NBL has been selected with their ten years' data starting from 2011/12 till 2020/21.

Main objective of this study is to find out financial performance of RBB, NBL and ADBL. Descriptive and analytical analyses have been done for the purpose by using various methodologies and based on the secondary data.

5.2 Conclusion

The study is based on the data of three government banks namely RBB, ADBL and NBL for ten Fiscal Years from 2011/12 to 2020/21. The thesis includes only secondary data and all the calculations and presentations are based on the secondary data. According to the analysis, the overall performance of the sample banks is found to be satisfactory. All the banks are not strong in performance. Some are strong in liquidity position and some are strong in profit making.

The average deposit of RBB is highest than ADBL and NBL during analysis period. Similarly, NBL is following to RBB in collecting deposit rather than ADBL. The total deposit of RBB is highest in all F/Y and NBL has lowest deposit collected in the entire period. ADBL has lowest amount of loan in 2011/12 i.e.4326.41 crores but it has aggressively collected highest deposit in succeeding F/Y. It shows that RBB is has good performance in collecting deposit from its valued customers.

RBB has highest and NBL has lowest NPL in average during analysis period. ADBL and NBL has lowest NPL in comparison to RBB. There is highest NPL in RBB and NBL in comparison to other ADBL. All are government banks and NPL in those banks are higher, shows the reckless lending and untidy long process in recovery

management. Similarly, the long process in decision regarding recovery management leads them to higher NPL in comparison to other private commercial banks.

The C/D ratio of RBB is 46.08 times at 2068/69 and 77.15 times at 2018/19. The average C/D ratio is 63.48. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. C/D ratio of RBB is still below than the standard. It means that it still has idle fund to invest in the market which shows good financial performance of the bank in analysis period. The C/D ratio of ADBL is 104.06 times at 2011/12 and 92.93 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio is 94.98. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. The ratio shows that how much of a bank's core funds are being used for lending, the main banking activity. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. C/D ratio of ADBL is higher than the standard. The C/D ratio of NBL is 52.98 times at 2011/12 and 82.76 times at 2020/21. The average C/D ratio of NBL is 70 times. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio is 80 times. A higher ratio indicates more reliance on deposits for lending. C/D ratio of NBL is almost at the standard. The average C/D ratio of RBB is 63.48 times, ADBL has 94.98 times whereas NBL 70 times. The maximum ratio of C/D ratio of RBB is 77.15 times, ADBL has 104.06 times whereas NBL has 82.76 times during analysis period. RBB and NBL is in comfort zone of C/D ratio while ADBL has to downsize of C/D ratio to meet the standard. To downsize either deposit volume is to be increased or loan amount is to be decreased.

The financial performance of RBB is greater than NBL and ADBL according to the loan disbursed. From the disbursed, RBB can collect highest amount of interest income, a major parameter of profit of the company. The deposit amount collected by the RBB is greater than ADBL and NBL. The deposit of NBL and ADBL is almost same in every F/Y. According to the deposit collected, the financial performance of RBB is good than ADBL and NBL. From the deposit collected, it can grant the loan to its valued customers.

According NPL, the performance of NBL is good than RBB and ADBL due to lowest NPL in comparison to the other sample commercial banks. The C/D ratio of ADBL is more than 100% whereas C/D ratio of RBB and NBL is lower than ABBL. The minimum standard of C/D ratio is 90 % now. The minimum C/D ratio explained the comfort zone of bank to lend in the credit in the market. According to the standard NBL has also maintained the C/D ratio under the standard but the performance of RBB is far better than ADBL and NBL.

ADBL is in comfort zone of CAR ratio while NBL and RBB has to increase the CAR ratio to protect depositors and promote stability and efficiency of financial systems around the world. The minimum standard of CAR till F/Y 2015/16 was 10 times. The minimum standard of CAR from F/Y 2016/17 is 11 times. The Capital adequacy ratio of ADBL is highest and above the minimum standard as set by the central bank whereas CAR of NBL and RBB is lower than ADBL. CAR of NBL and RBB is even negative in starting of F/Y. According to CAR the financial performance of ADBL is far better than NBL and RBB.

Banks have to prove that they are the potential contributors to the national economy ensuring adequate rate of return on investment, efficient and viable agencies for mobilization of savings and its channels into productive sectors and strategically well planned to be competitive with competitors and other agencies and are trustworthy.

5.3 Implications

Based on the analysis, interpretation & conclusions, some recommendations are made here so that the concerned authorities, future researchers, academicians, bankers can get some insights on the present conditions on above topics. It is assumed that this research will be profitable to improve the current situation as well as for the grounding of further researches.

On the basis of the major findings some important suggestions have been forwarded so that they might help the sample banks to strengthen weaker aspects of the financial activities.

- Loans and advances to Total Deposit ratio are good for both the banks, but the banks should not invest more in similar and non-productive sectors. There should be good portfolio in the investment sector of the banks. They should also search the productive sectors for investment. It leads to the increase in the interest income as well as profit of the bank.
- Banks should maintain liquidity ratio for the daily cash transactions. All the deposit should not be invested in loans and advances. Some percentages of deposit is to be kept in the banks for fulfilling the required demand of the customer. Standard liquidity ratio is 2:1, but here both the bank's current ratio is seen to be lower than this. Therefore, the sample banks should modify their working capital policy to maintain the standard ratio.

- Debt financing exceeds 80%. It indicates excessively geared capital structure. Since debt financing need to pay regular interest, they are high burden to the banks. Therefore, they should try to decrease the debt financing and increase the equity financing for which dividend is to be paid which is obviously lower than the interest.
- Inconsistency is seen in the growth of the commercial banks. Banks are therefore suggested to predict more accurate data in order to remain in the same position.
- ADBL has C/D ratio more than the standard set by central bank so it should maintain the C/D ratio as standard set by central bank.
- The success of the banking sector depends upon the banking awareness of the general public. Unless they find a convincing reason about their savings, it is almost impossible for the banks to sustain. For this there should be awareness program time to time. This will help the general public to know about the new schemes of the banks and good reasons for their savings.
- Today is the age of competition; banks have to survive within these competitions. Therefore, for the attraction of the general public, there should be attractive programs, facilities, technologies like- ATM, credit cards, 365 days banking, etc.
- Fixed deposits are the deposits deposited for long time period and need to pay higher interest. Therefore, much fixed deposits are to be used for the long time investment and generate income for the bank.
- Banks play the vital role in the development of the economy of the country. However, all the banks have satisfactory performance, there is situation of inflation, which is a cause of narrow scope operation. So, banks have to prove that they are the potential contributors to the national economy ensuring adequate rate on investment.

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Relationship loan and advances with deposit of RBB		
Year	Total Deposit in Rs (a)	Total Loan in Rs(b)
2011/12	8778	3045
2012/13	9109	4905
2013/14	10727	6085
2014/15	12422	7584
2015/16	14621	8547
2016/17	15358	10643
2017/18	16933	12087
2018/19	19199	14812
2019/20	23298	15652
2020/21	26620	19597
correlation (a,b)	0.99	
Coefficient of determination(r^2)	0.97	
covariance (a,b)	30843872.61	

Relationship loan and advances with deposit of ADBL		
Year	Total Deposit in Rs (a)	Total Loan in Rs(b)
2011/12	4326.41	4498.84
2012/13	5447.76	5491.85
2013/14	6589.84	6247.29
2014/15	7703.5	7223.85
2015/16	8738.7	8341.83
2016/17	9981.6	9770.31
2017/18	10473.1	10398.72
2018/19	11936.3	11175.02
2019/20	14373.2	12337.71
2020/21	16299	15147.07
correlation (a,b)	0.99	
Coefficient of determination(r^2)	0.99	
covariance (a,b)	12693456.88	

Relationship loan and advances with deposit of NBL		
Year	Total Deposit in Rs (a)	Total Loan in Rs(b)
2011/12	5605.2	2969.9
2012/13	6298.4	3785.2
2013/14	6933.8	4121.8
2014/15	7799.99	5338.8
2015/16	8941	6352.4
2016/17	9394.4	7318.6
2017/18	9983.1	7829.6
2018/19	11827.5	9572.5
2019/20	14298.9	10683
2020/21	16362.3	14195.91
correlation (a,b)	0.99	
Coefficient of determination(r^2)	0.98	
covariance (a,b)	12160066.00	

Trend Analysis of Loan of RBB

Year (X)	Loan (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	3045	-4.5	20.25	9272025	-13702.5
2013	4905	-3.5	12.25	24059025	-17167.5
2014	6085	-2.5	6.25	37027225	-15212.5
2015	7584	-1.5	2.25	57517056	-11376
2016	8547	-0.5	0.25	73051209	-4273.5
2017	10643	0.5	0.25	113273449	5321.5
2018	12087	1.5	2.25	146095569	18130.5
2019	14812	2.5	6.25	219395344	37030
2020	15652	3.5	12.25	244985104	54782
2021	19597	4.5	20.25	384042409	88186.5
	$\Sigma Y=102957$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.50$	$\Sigma Y^2=1308718415$	$\Sigma xY =141718.50$

Where $N = 10$

We have $Y = a + bx \dots \dots \dots (i)$

$\Sigma Y = na + b \Sigma x \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

$\Sigma xY = a \Sigma x + b \Sigma x^2 \dots \dots \dots (iii)$

Putting the value of $\Sigma Y, \Sigma x, \Sigma xY, \Sigma X^2 \Sigma X^2$ and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$$102957 = 10a + b0 \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

$$141718.50 = a0 + b82.50 \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$$a = 10295.70$$

$$b = 1717.80$$

We have $Y = 10295.70 + 1717.80x \dots \dots \dots (i)$

Forecasting Loan

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y=10295.70+1717.80x$
2022	5.5	19743.60
2023	6.5	21461.40
2024	7.5	23179.20
2025	8.5	24897.00
2026	9.5	26614.80

Trend Analysis of Loan of ADBL

Year (X)	Loan (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	4498.84	-4.5	20.25	20239561.35	-20244.78
2013	5491.85	-3.5	12.25	30160416.42	-19221.475
2014	6247.29	-2.5	6.25	39028632.34	-15618.225
2015	7223.85	-1.5	2.25	52184008.82	-10835.775
2016	8341.83	-0.5	0.25	69586127.75	-4170.915
2017	9770.31	0.5	0.25	95458957.5	4885.155
2018	10398.72	1.5	2.25	108133377.6	15598.08
2019	11175.02	2.5	6.25	124881072	27937.55
2020	12337.71	3.5	12.25	152219088	43181.985
2021	15147.07	4.5	20.25	229433729.6	68161.815
	$\Sigma Y=90632.49$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=921324971.40$	$\Sigma xY = 89673.42$

Where $N = 10$

We have $Y = a + bx \dots \dots \dots (i)$

$\Sigma Y = na + b \Sigma x \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

$\Sigma xY = a \Sigma x + b \Sigma x^2 \dots \dots \dots (iii)$

Putting the value of $\Sigma Y, \Sigma x, \Sigma xY, \Sigma x^2$ and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$90632.49 = 10a + b0 \dots \dots \dots (iv)$

$89673.42 = a0 + b82.5 \dots \dots \dots (v)$

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 9063.25$

$b = 1086.95$

We have $Y = 9063.25 + 1086.95x \dots \dots \dots (i)$

Forecasting Loan

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 9063.25 + 1086.95x$
2022	5.5	15041.48
2023	6.5	16128.43
2024	7.5	17215.38
2025	8.5	18302.33
2026	9.5	19389.28

Trend Analysis of Loan of NBL

Year (X)	Loan (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	2969.9	-4.5	20.25	8820306.01	-13364.55
2013	3785.2	-3.5	12.25	14327739.04	-13248.2
2014	4121.8	-2.5	6.25	16989235.24	-10304.5
2015	5338.8	-1.5	2.25	28502785.44	-8008.2
2016	6352.4	-0.5	0.25	40352985.76	-3176.2
2017	7318.6	0.5	0.25	53561905.96	3659.3
2018	7829.6	1.5	2.25	61302636.16	11744.4
2019	9572.5	2.5	6.25	91632756.25	23931.25
2020	10683	3.5	12.25	114126489	37390.5
2021	14195.91	4.5	20.25	201523860.7	63881.595
	$\Sigma Y=72167.71$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=631140699.60$	$\Sigma xY = 92505.40$

Where $N = 10$

We have $Y = a + bx \dots \dots \dots (i)$

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2 \dots \dots \dots (iii)$

Putting the value of $\Sigma Y, \Sigma x, \Sigma xY, \Sigma X^2 \Sigma X^2$ and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$72167.71 = 10a + b0 \dots \dots \dots (iv)$

$92505.40 = a0 + b82.5 \dots \dots \dots (v)$

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 7216.77$

$b = 1121.28$

We have $Y = 7216.77 + 1121.28x \dots \dots \dots (i)$

Forecasting Loan

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 7216.77 + 1121.28x$
2022	5.5	13383.81
2023	6.5	14505.09
2024	7.5	15626.37
2025	8.5	16747.65
2026	9.5	17868.93

Trend Analysis of ROA of RBB

Year (X)	ROA (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	1.23	-4.5	20.25	1.51	-5.54
2013	1.26	-3.5	12.25	1.59	-4.41
2014	1.47	-2.5	6.25	2.16	-3.68
2015	3.22	-1.5	2.25	10.37	-4.83
2016	1.42	-0.5	0.25	2.02	-0.71
2017	1.6	0.5	0.25	2.56	0.80
2018	1.42	1.5	2.25	2.02	2.13
2019	2.23	2.5	6.25	4.97	5.58
2020	1.64	3.5	12.25	2.69	5.74
2021	1.1	4.5	20.25	1.21	4.95
	$\Sigma Y=16.59$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.50$	$\Sigma Y^2=31.10$	$\Sigma xY =0.03$

Where N =10

We have $Y = a + bx$(i)

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x$(ii)

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2$(iii)

Putting the value of ΣY , Σx , ΣxY , ΣX^2 and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$16.59 = 10a + b0$(iv)

$0.03 = a0 + b82.50$(v)

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 1.66$

$b = 0.0004$

We have $Y = 1.66 + 0.0004x$(i)

Forecasting ROA

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y=1.66+0.0004x$
2022	5.5	1.66
2023	6.5	1.66
2024	7.5	1.66
2025	8.5	1.66
2026	9.5	1.66

Trend Analysis of ROA of ADBL

Year (X)	Loan (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	2.9	-4.5	20.25	8.41	-13.05
2013	2.97	-3.5	12.25	8.82	-10.40
2014	1.76	-2.5	6.25	3.10	-4.40
2015	3.12	-1.5	2.25	9.73	-4.68
2016	2.32	-0.5	0.25	5.38	-1.16
2017	2.15	0.5	0.25	4.62	1.08
2018	2.71	1.5	2.25	7.34	4.07
2019	2.77	2.5	6.25	7.67	6.93
2020	1.86	3.5	12.25	3.46	6.51
2021	1.59	4.5	20.25	2.53	7.16
	$\Sigma Y=24.15$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=61.07$	$\Sigma xY =-7.95$

Where N =10

We have $Y = a + bx$(i)

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x$(ii)

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2$(iii)

Putting the value of ΣY , Σx , ΣxY , ΣX^2 ΣX^2 and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$24.15 = 10a + b0$(iv)

$(7.95) = a0 + b82.5$(v)

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 2.42$

$b = (0.10)$

We have $Y = 2.42 - 0.1x$(i)

Forecasting ROA

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 2.42 - 0.1x$
2022	5.5	1.87
2023	6.5	1.77
2024	7.5	1.67
2025	8.5	1.57
2026	9.5	1.47

Trend Analysis of ROA of NBL

Year (X)	Loan (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	0.3	-4.5	20.25	0.09	-1.35
2013	1.07	-3.5	12.25	1.14	-3.75
2014	0.92	-2.5	6.25	0.85	-2.30
2015	0.55	-1.5	2.25	0.30	-0.83
2016	2.79	-0.5	0.25	7.78	-1.40
2017	2.78	0.5	0.25	7.73	1.39
2018	2.41	1.5	2.25	5.81	3.62
2019	1.51	2.5	6.25	2.28	3.78
2020	1.22	3.5	12.25	1.49	4.27
2021	1.33	4.5	20.25	1.77	5.99
	$\Sigma Y=14.88$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=29.24$	$\Sigma xY = 9.42$

Where $N = 10$

We have $Y = a + bx \dots \dots \dots (i)$

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2 \dots \dots \dots (iii)$

Putting the value of $\Sigma Y, \Sigma x, \Sigma xY, \Sigma X^2 \Sigma X^2$ and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$14.88 = 10a + b0 \dots \dots \dots (iv)$

$9.42 = a0 + b82.5 \dots \dots \dots (v)$

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 1.49$

$b = 0.11$

We have $Y = 1.49 + 0.11x \dots \dots \dots (i)$

Forecasting Loan

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 1.49 + 0.11x$
2022	5.5	2.10
2023	6.5	2.21
2024	7.5	2.32
2025	8.5	2.43
2026	9.5	2.54

Trend Analysis of Deposit of RBB

Year (X)	Deposit (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	8778	-4.5	20.25	77053284	-39501
2013	9109	-3.5	12.25	82973881	-31881.5
2014	10727	-2.5	6.25	115068529	-26817.5
2015	12422	-1.5	2.25	154306084	-18633
2016	14621	-0.5	0.25	213773641	-7310.5
2017	15358	0.5	0.25	235868164	7679
2018	16933	1.5	2.25	286726489	25399.5
2019	19199	2.5	6.25	368601601	47997.5
2020	23298	3.5	12.25	542796804	81543
2021	26620	4.5	20.25	708624400	119790
	$\Sigma Y=157065$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=2785792877$	$\Sigma xY = 158265.5$

Where $N = 10$

We have $Y = a + bx \dots \dots \dots (i)$

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2 \dots \dots \dots (iii)$

Putting the value of $\Sigma Y, \Sigma x, \Sigma xY, \Sigma X^2 \Sigma X^2$ and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$157065 = 10a + b0 \dots \dots \dots (iv)$

$158265.5 = a0 + b82.5 \dots \dots \dots (v)$

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 15706.5$

$b = 1918.37$

We have $Y = 15706.5 + 1918.37x \dots \dots \dots (i)$

Forecasting Deposit

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 15706.5 + 1918.37x$
2022	5.5	27257.54
2023	6.5	28175.91
2024	7.5	30094.28
2025	8.5	32012.65
2026	9.5	33931.02

Trend Analysis of Deposit of ADBL

Year (X)	Deposit (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	4326.41	-4.5	20.25	18717823.49	-19468.845
2013	5447.76	-3.5	12.25	29678089.02	-19067.16
2014	6589.84	-2.5	6.25	43425991.23	-16474.6
2015	7703.5	-1.5	2.25	59343912.25	-11555.25
2016	8738.7	-0.5	0.25	76364877.69	-4369.35
2017	9981.6	0.5	0.25	99632338.56	4990.8
2018	10473.1	1.5	2.25	109685823.6	15709.65
2019	11936.3	2.5	6.25	142475257.7	29840.75
2020	14373.2	3.5	12.25	206588878.2	50306.2
2021	16299	4.5	20.25	265657401	73345.5
	$\Sigma Y=95869.41$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=1051570393$	$\Sigma xY = 103257.70$

Where N = 10

We have $Y = a + bx$(i)

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x$(ii)

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2$(iii)

Putting the value of ΣY , Σx , ΣxY , Σx^2 and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$95869.41 = 10a + b0$(iv)

$103257.70 = a0 + b82.5$(v)

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 9586.94$

$b = 1251.61$

We have $Y = 9586.94 + 1251.61x$(i)

Forecasting Deposit

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 9586.94 + 1251.61x$
2022	5.5	16470.80
2023	6.5	17722.41
2024	7.5	18974.02
2025	8.5	20225.63
2026	9.5	21477.24

Trend Analysis of Deposit of NBL

Year (X)	Deposit (Y)	$x=X-2016.5$	x^2	Y^2	xY
2012	5605.2	-4.5	20.25	31418267.04	-25223.4
2013	6298.4	-3.5	12.25	39669842.56	-22044.4
2014	6933.8	-2.5	6.25	48077582.44	-17334.5
2015	7799.99	-1.5	2.25	60839844	-11699.985
2016	8941	-0.5	0.25	79941481	-4470.5
2017	9394.4	0.5	0.25	88254751.36	4697.2
2018	9983.1	1.5	2.25	99662285.61	14974.65
2019	11827.5	2.5	6.25	139889756.3	29568.75
2020	14298.9	3.5	12.25	204458541.2	50046.15
2021	16362.3	4.5	20.25	267724861.3	73630.35
	$\Sigma Y=97444.59$	$\Sigma x=0$	$\Sigma x^2=82.5$	$\Sigma Y^2=1059937213$	$\Sigma xY = 92144.32$

Where N =10

We have $Y = a + bx$(i)

$\Sigma Y = na + b\Sigma x$(ii)

$\Sigma xY = a\Sigma x + b\Sigma x^2$(iii)

Putting the value of ΣY , Σx , ΣxY , ΣX^2 ΣX^2 and n in above equation (ii) and (iii) then we get,

$97444.59 = 10a + b0$(iv)

$92144.32 = a0 + b82.5$(v)

Now solving this equation (iv) and (v) then we get,

$a = 9744.46$

$b = 1116.90$

We have $Y = 9744.46 + 1116.90x$(i)

Forecasting Deposit

Year(X)	$x=X-2016.5$	$Y = 9744.46 + 1116.90x$
2022	5.5	15887.41
2023	6.5	17004.31
2024	7.5	18121.21
2025	8.5	19238.11
2026	9.5	20355.01

Tribhuvan University
Faculty of Management
Janamaitri Multiple Campus

MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of
Commerical Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2079/05/15

Work Completed: Proposal for Dissertation

Comments of Supervisor

- Proposal should follow the "Master's Degree Dissertation Guidelines 2019" as provided by T.U. management.
- Proper citation is needed in the report.
- Problem statement and objective should be specific.
- Page number should be on the top right side of the pages.
- Line should be 1.5 in all text lines.
- Latest literature review must be included in the report.

(Add separate sheet if necessary)

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Signature of Supervisor

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MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of
Commerical Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2079/06/14

Work Completed: Chapter I

Comments of Supervisor

- Problem statement and objective should be consistent.
- Limitation should be recoded point wise.
- Use active verbs i.e. examine, analyze, etc.
- Research Gap should be specific.
- Citation should be in proper formatting
(Add Separate sheet if necessary)

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MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of
Commerical Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2079/07/17

Work Completed: Chapter II

Comments of Supervisor

- Read teh literature on related so to intensify your knowledge.
- Add latest article for review of literature
- Add figure for conceptual framework at the end of this capture
- Put the literature review on chronological order.

(Add separate sheet if necessary)

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Signature of Supervisor

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MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of Commercial Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2079/08/18

Work Completed: Chapter III

Comments of Supervisor

- Define analysis method clearly.
- For validity and reliability specify clearly validity and reliability of the data
- Sources of data collection should be clearly stated.
- Clarify the population and sample size for this study
(Add separate sheet if necessary)

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MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of
Commerical Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2079/09/29

Work Completed: IV

Comments of Supervisor

- Sources of Data Must be cited.
- Table and charts should describe briefly.
- Show the name of table and chart.
- Discuss the previous findings
- Source of finding should be included
- Include major findings

(Add separate sheet if necessary)

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MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of
Commerical Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2080/01/12

Work Completed: V

Comments of Supervisor

- Finding should be based on the analysis of the data
- Should provide all the information about the finding of the study.
- Implications should be point wise (bulleted)
- Work is satisfactory

(Add separate sheet if necessary)

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Signature of Supervisor

Tribhuvan University
Faculty of Management
Janamaitri Multiple Campus

MBS Dissertation Progress Report

Name of Student: Sagar Thapa

Name of Supervisor: Dan Bahadur Palli

Topic of Dissertation: Fund Management and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of Commercial Banks

Proposal Defense Date: 2079/03/26

Supervisor Consultation Date: 2080/03/03

Work Completed: All Chapter, Final Report

Comments of Supervisor

- Check for whether page formatting like, page layout, margin, indentation, line spacing.
(Should be as per TU dissertation guideline 2019)
- Check for Grammar.
- Check for Different part such as Heading, Body and Ending.
- Prepare for the Viva and Presentation of slide on power point.

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Signature of Supervisor